

Polymerase and Proofreading Exonuclease Domains in the DNA Polymerase γ and Nuclear-encoded RNA Polymerase of the Human Mitochondria and Identification of Mitochondrial Disease Mutations in the Polymerase Active Site Region of DNA Polymerase γ

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Abstract

Recent reports have made it clear that mutations in the mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) polymerase γ (POLG1) are a major cause of many human diseases. Mutations in the mtDNA polymerase leads to defective oxidative phosphorylation and ATP production, resulting in many mitochondrial diseases. For their mitochondrial genome replication, humans and animals use POLG1, whose catalytic site is essentially similar to the *E. coli* DNA polymerase I (DNA pol I). Multiple sequence alignment (MSA) analysis have shown that the POLG1 and *E. coli* DNA pol I use identical amino acids in their polymerase catalytic sites, viz. $^{-943}R^{-4}EHAKI^1FNYGRI_{955}Y^8G^{-}$ (human DNA pol γ) as $^{-4}RSAKA^1INFGLIY^8G^{-}$ (*E. coli* DNA pol I). However, the human POLG1 shows only 31.25% identity with the *E. coli* DNA pol I, suggesting a highly divergent evolution. Mutation(s) in the POLG1 gene is one of the most common causes of many inherited mitochondrial diseases in children and adults. Depending on their location within the enzyme, mutations either lead to mtDNA depletion or accumulation of multiple mtDNA deletions leading to various mitochondrial diseases. The most common POLG1 dominant mutation, viz. Y955→H/C, which lead to a severe, early-onset of multi-systemic mitochondrial disease with bilateral sensorineural hearing loss, cataract, myopathy, and liver failure is located in the template-binding pair of the polymerase catalytic site region by MSA. Another dominant mutation, R943→H/C is observed in patients with Progressive External Ophthalmoplegia (adPEO, an autosomal, dominant, heritable mitochondrial disorder) is located in the nucleoside triphosphate (NTP) selection amino acid in the polymerase catalytic site region. The nuclear-encoded RNA polymerase (NEP) is imported from the nucleus and involves in the transcription of all the mitochondrial genes. The human mitochondrial NEP showed 39.30%, 40.12% and 26.98% identities to the NEPs of the mitochondria and chloroplasts of *Arabidopsis thaliana*, and T7 RNA polymerase, respectively, suggesting that the human and plant mitochondrial NEPs are distinctly different. Interestingly, the human NEP's catalytic core is almost completely conserved in the plant mitochondrial and chloroplast NEPs, viz. $^{-4}KVVKQ^1TVMTVVY^8G^{-}$ (Human) and $^{-4}KLVKQ^1TVMTSVY^8G^{-}$ (*A. Thaliana*). Furthermore, the mitochondrial NEP's catalytic core from human and different animal sources is remarkably conserved and is in close agreement with other NEPs of plant sources. Both the human DNA pol γ and NEP possess a typical template-binding pair (-YG-), a basic catalytic amino acid (K) to initiate catalysis and a basic nucleotide selection amino acid R at -4 from the catalytic K. The PR exonucleases of POLG1 and NEP belong to the DEDD-superfamily of exonucleases and uses a Y or H as the proton acceptor, respectively.

Keywords: Human mitochondria; Human mitochondrial diseases; DNA Polymerase γ ; Nuclear-encoded RNA polymerase; Polymerase active sites; Proofreading exonucleases; Proofreading exonuclease active sites

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1. Introduction

Mitochondria are found in all eukaryotes and play a crucial role in generating the much needed biological energy for the cells in the form of adenosine triphosphates (ATPs). They are semi-autonomous organelles, partly controlled by their own genome and mostly by the nuclear imports. They are double-membrane structures and harbour both the mitochondrial genome (mtDNA), which are double-stranded, circular molecules and mitochondrial plasmids. Interestingly, it is the only organelle in animals other than the nucleus, with its own DNA. Not only the mitochondrial sizes vary from 0.5 to 4 μm , but also their copy numbers and shapes vary considerably in different cell types and under different physiological conditions. Generally, about dozens of mtDNA copies are found in a single mitochondrion. As a single eukaryotic cell harbours 100s of mitochondria, the mtDNAs usually exceed > 1000 copies per cell.

The main function of mitochondria is to generate energy for cellular activities in the form of ATPs via oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS) by the process known as aerobic respiration and hence, they are known as the 'power house' of the cells. In addition to ATP generation, mitochondria also perform a variety of other cellular functions like forming Fe-S clusters, haem and amino acids, and $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ handling, regulation of signalling pathways through the release of cytochrome *c*, immune responses, inflammation, etc. Mitochondrial reactive oxygen species (mROS), generated during OXPHOS, affects the redox state of cells and has emerged as signalling molecules to communicate between cells [1]. Nemoto et al., [2] have shown that the mROS not only regulate cellular metabolism, but also is involved in tumour necrosis factor receptor signalling. Thus, the mitochondrial functions extend beyond the boundaries of the cells and influence an organism's physiology by regulating communication between cells and tissues [3]. Mitochondria also contribute to various cellular stress responses such as autophagy and apoptosis. Therefore, the mitochondrial functions are central to the physiology of humans and, consequently, "mitochondrial dysfunction" and has been implicated in a wide range of human diseases. In humans and most multicellular organisms, the mitochondrial mode of inheritance is strictly maternal, i.e., the mtDNA is inherited from the mother as the sperm mtDNA is actively degraded immediately after fertilization [4, 5].

1.1. mtDNA

mtDNA is organized into discrete nucleoid complexes in the mitochondrial matrix with tightly associated proteins responsible for its replication and maintenance, but with no histone(s). They are partly controlled by its own genome and mostly by nuclear imports. Replication of mitochondrial genome is independent of cell-cycle with individual mtDNA molecules being randomly selected for replication, a phenomenon referred to as relaxed replication. Human and animal mtDNAs are compact in structure and typically lack introns in all of their genes, except in 2 tRNAs (introns of ~1 kb are located between the tRNA^{Phe} and tRNA^{Pro} genes), whereas introns are very common in nuclear DNAs. Human mtDNA is a 16,569-base pair closed-circular molecule, encoding 13 polypeptides required for OXPHOS and 24 non-coding genes, which includes specialized tRNAs and rRNAs (12S and 16S), needed for translation within the organelle [6]. These genes are encoded asymmetrically between the two mtDNA strands, denoted heavy and light. The heavy strand encodes 2 rRNAs, 14 tRNAs and 12 mRNAs and the light strand encodes 8 tRNAs and 1 mRNA. All 13 polypeptides are in the mitochondrial respiratory chain complex (OXPHOS) and the remaining > 67 OXPHOS subunits are nuclear-encoded. In fact, a vast majority of the proteins present in the mammalian mitochondria (~1500 different types) are encoded by nuclear DNA, but the genes for some, if not most of them, are thought to have originally been of bacterial origin, and have been transferred to the nucleus during evolution. Mitochondria also exhibit heteroplasmy, i.e., the presence of different mtDNA sequences (both wild-type and mutant ones) within the same organelle in a cell. Mutations in mtDNA cause a wide variety of neurological, muscular, and tissue degenerative diseases which as many as 1/2000 persons are at a life-time risk [7, 8].

1.2. Mitochondrial Diseases

Mitochondrial diseases are a group of genetic disorders that are characterized by mutations in genes in the nuclear DNA (nDNA) and/or mtDNA that encode proteins involved in mitochondrial functions. Mitochondrial diseases include: Mitochondrial myopathy, Neuropathy, Diabetes mellitus and Deafness (DAD) (this combination at an early age can be due to mitochondrial disease), Leber's Hereditary Optic Neuropathy (LHON), Leigh syndrome (subacute necrotizing encephalomyelopathy), Dementia, Neuropathy Ataxia Retinitis Pigmentosa and Ptosis (NARPP), Myoneurogenic Gastrointestinal Encephalopathy (MNGIE), progressive Myoclonic Epilepsy and "Ragged Red Fibres" (MERRF) syndrome, Mitochondrial Encephalopathy Lactic Acidosis and Stroke-like episodes (MELAS) syndrome, Mitochondrial DNA depletion syndrome (MDS) or Alper's disease. (Alpers' disease and other *POLG1* gene-related disorders are part of a larger family of mitochondrial DNA depletion disorders. Homozygous or compound heterozygous mutations cause severe deficiency of mitochondrial DNA pol γ , leading to depletion of mtDNA which results in mitochondrial dysfunction). Patients with *POLG1* mutations present PEO, a disease characterized by weakness of the ocular muscles and myopathy secondary to the depletion of mitochondria. Ataxia neuropathy spectrum (ANS) is a group of *POLG1*-

related disorders in which patients have difficulties with coordination along with nerve dysfunction. Alpers-Huttenlocher syndrome (AHS), which affects children is the classical form of hepatocerebral MDS, and it has been again attributed to mutations in *POLG1*. Mutations in mitochondrial tRNAs can be responsible for severe diseases like MELAS and MERRF syndromes [9]. Mutations of mtDNA can also lead to a number of other illnesses like exercise intolerance and Kearns–Sayre syndrome (KSS), which causes a person to lose full function of heart, eye, and muscle movements.

1.2.1. mtDNA-associated Diseases

Mitochondrial dysfunction is associated with a large number of common diseases, such as neurodegenerative disorders like Alzheimer's disease (AD), Huntington's disease (HD), Parkinson's disease (PD), bipolar disorder, schizophrenia, and cardiomyopathies, metabolic syndrome, obesity, diabetes, aging and senescence, anxiety disorders, sarcopenia (gradual loss of muscle mass, strength and function in elderly), chronic fatigue syndrome, etc. [3 and reference therein]. Several lines of evidence indicate that dysregulation of mitochondrial function plays an important role in cancer biology also [10, 11]. For example, data available from the International Cancer Genome Consortium (ICGC) and The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA), have demonstrated that ~60% of all solid tumours bear at least one mtDNA mutation. Therefore, it is clear that mtDNA mutations are of a very common occurrence across all solid tumours [12]. Moreover, large-scale sequencing efforts and clinical studies have confirmed the prevalence of mutations in mtDNA in human tumours and their potential roles in cancer progression. More specifically, mutations in the *POLG1* gene have also been reported in breast cancers [13]. Some evidence also suggests that mtDNA mutations might be a major contributor to the aging process and age-associated pathologies [14].

1.2.2. mtDNA Damage and Neurodegenerative Diseases

Point mutations, deletions, duplication or sometimes loss of entire mtDNA are implicated as the causes of aging and several neurodegenerative diseases (caused by the progressive loss of structure or function of neurons). AD, a most common form of dementia, is a brain disorder that slowly destroys memory and thinking skills, and eventually, interferes even with daily tasks. It is found that the brains of individuals with AD have elevated levels of oxidative DNA damage in both nDNA and mtDNA, but the mtDNA has approximately 10-fold higher levels of oxidative DNA damage than nDNA. This is because the mtDNA is associated with the mitochondrial inner membrane which is the site of oxidative phosphorylation and generation of large amount of mROS and H₂O₂. In AD, it has been proposed that aged mitochondria are the critical factor in the origin of neurodegeneration. Analysis of the brains of AD patients suggested an impaired function of the mtDNA repair pathway, which would cause reduced overall quality of their mtDNA [15].

HD is an autosomal, dominant genetic disorder. In HD patients, the mutant Huntingtin protein causes mitochondrial dysfunction by inhibition of mitochondrial electron transport and increased levels of mROS, leading to oxidative stress. Thus, the mutant Huntingtin protein promotes oxidative damage to mtDNA, as well as nDNA, that may contribute to the Huntington's disease pathology [16].

PD is a chronic neurologic condition named after Dr. James Parkinson, who first described the syndrome in 1817. PD is a slowly progressive disease, which causes a gradual loss of the nerve cells in the brain that produce the neurotransmitter dopamine. Dopamine carries signals to the part of the brain that control movement and coordination. Therefore, decreased dopamine levels leads to unintended or uncontrollable movements, such as shaking, stiffness, and difficulty with balancing and coordination. PD symptoms usually begin gradually and worsen over time. Again, mtDNA damage is also implicated in PD. To investigate mtDNA damage as a potential blood-based marker for PD, Qi et al., [17] have recently developed a PCR-based assay which allows accurate real-time quantification of mtDNA damage in a scalable platform.

Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) is a rare neurodegenerative disease that results in the progressive loss of motor neurons of the brain and spinal cord that control voluntary muscles. The DNA oxidation product 8-oxoguanine (8-oxoG) is a well-established marker of oxidative DNA damage. In persons with ALS, the enzymes that normally repair 8-oxoG DNA damages in the mtDNA of spinal motor neurons are impaired leading to oxidative damage to mtDNA of motor neurons, which is suggested as a significant factor in the etiology of ALS [18].

1.3. mtDNA Replication and mtDNA Polymerase

mtDNA replication is a post-mitotic process and occurs throughout the organism's lifetime. Initiating mtDNA replication involves a process known as priming, where short RNA primers are synthesized by the pol α -associated primase (PriS/Pri1-DNA Primase small subunit), that the DNA polymerase can use as a foundation for 3'-synthesis during the

replication process. After POLG1 has finished replication of the full mitochondrial genome, the primers are removed by an RNase, and the resultant gaps are filled with dNTPs by a repair polymerase and finally ligated by a ligase [19]. The mitochondrial replication machinery consists of not only the DNA polymerase complex, but also other proteins like TWINKLE and mitochondrial single-strand binding (SSB) proteins. (TWINKLE is a helicase that unwinds short stretches of dsDNA in the 5'→3' direction and the SSB maintain the two strands separated for polymerase to proceed with DNA synthesis). All these polypeptides for replication, including the POLG1 are encoded by the nuclear genome [20].

Whereas several DNA polymerases are required to replicate nDNA, DNA pol γ (POLG1) is the sole polymerase responsible for mitochondrial DNA replication and repair. The mitochondrial DNA polymerase (EC 2.7.7.7) belongs to Family A polymerase (Family A polymerases are found both in pro-and eukaryotes and possess two exonuclease domains, (both 5'→3' and 3'→5' exonucleases), like bacterial DNA pol I, T7 DNA pol, pol θ and pol ν). Therefore, POLG1 is structurally homologous to the T7 DNA pol and *E. coli* DNA pol I. However, in contrast to T7 DNA pol and *E. coli* DNA pol I, the mitochondrial DNA pol γ consists of two subunits: a large subunit (POLG1) with DNA polymerase and proofreading 3'→5' exonuclease activities, and a small subunit (POLG2) which confers high fidelity to POLG1 [21, 22]. The DNA pol γ holoenzyme is a heterotrimeric complex and comprised of two nuclear-encoded subunits, viz. the POLG1 and POLG2, where POLG2 exists as dimer). The POLG2 mediates high-affinity binding of the holoenzyme to the template DNA, primer recognition and enhances DNA pol γ processivity to several folds. Furthermore, POLG2 also confers high fidelity to POLG1, which is approximately 100-fold greater than that of nuclear polymerases.

The DNA pol γ complex, which is composed of a 140 kDa catalytic DNA polymerase subunit, encoded by the *POLG1* gene, and two 55 kDa accessory subunits, encoded by the *POLG2* gene. The *POLG1* gene is 21kb in size and comprises of 4,465 bp including a 282 bp 5'-untranslated region (UTR) and a 463 bp 3'-UTR and 23 exons spanning approximately 18.5 kb. The *POLG1* protein is synthesized as a precursor, containing an amino-terminal leader sequence (residues 1-25) that targets the protein to mitochondria and is cleaved-off after the import. The mature 140 kDa protein is divided into three functional domains: i) a 3'→5' exonuclease (exo) domain, ii) a linker domain, and iii) a highly conserved carboxy-terminal polymerase (pol) domain. The *POLG1* gene is located on the long arm of human chromosome 15, and it maps to 15q25, whereas the *POLG2* gene is located on Chromosome17q21 [23]. The *POLG1* is an acidic protein with a pI of 6.46 and the *POLG2* is highly basic with a pI of 8.64, suggesting its DNA binding property.

The mtDNA is placed in a highly oxidative environment in mitochondria. Therefore, it is vulnerable to high levels of mROS, leading to mutations, which possibly could result in cellular transformations and eventually leading to cancer. This is because the mROS can modify the structural properties of DNA bases and thus, damage the mtDNA. Upon exposure of cells to oxidative stress, a highly mutagenic damage to the DNA is done due to 7,8-dihydro-8-oxo-guanine (8-oxo-G). The 8-oxo-G is a major oxidative lesion and promutagenic. In general, the replicative DNA polymerases inaccurately bypass the lesions and tend to incorporate dATP opposite to the 8-oxo-G, leading to C:G to A:T transversion mutations. It should be noted that these mutations are among the most predominant somatic mutations in lung, breast, ovarian, gastric and colorectal cancers [24]. To circumvent this problem, the replicative polymerase, POLG1, is equipped with a 3'→5' PR exonuclease and an intrinsic deoxyribose-5-phosphate (dRP)-lyase activities. The (dRP)-lyase, as a part of the base excision repair (BER) pathway, acts as the primary and essential repair system for the removal of damaged mtDNA bases. It essentially removes the damaged bases by the oxidation by mROS in the mitochondrial genome. In this pathway, a DNA-damage-specific glycosylase removes the damaged base from the DNA by cleaving the bond between the base and the deoxyribose which creates an apurinic or apyrimidinic (AP) site. In the next step, an AP endonuclease nicks at the sugar backbone of the damaged DNA at the AP site. Thus, the AP endonuclease generates 3'-OH and 5'-dRP on the DNA strand. Now the 5'-dRP is removed by the (5'-dRP)-lyase and the gap is filled by a repair polymerase with correct dNTP and the gap is sealed by the DNA ligase I [25]. Interestingly, as POLG1 is the only DNA polymerase known to function in human and animal mitochondria [26], its efficiency in the repair system is very important to replicate the mtDNA without any mismatch. Substituting Ala for two essential acidic residues in the PR exonuclease motif, selectively eliminated the 3'→5' exonucleolytic function [27].

1.3.1. *POLG1* gene Mutations and Inherited Mitochondrial Diseases

More than one hundred pathogenic mutations have been reported on this enzyme alone since it was first described [28]. Mutations are found in all three domains of POLG1 protein [29]. Such *POLG1* mutations are known to lead to mtDNA depletion, which is known as mtDNA depletion syndrome (MDS) in humans. Furthermore, mutations in the *POLG1* gene have emerged directly or indirectly, as one of the most common causes of many mitochondrial diseases in children and adults. For example, they are responsible for a heterogeneous group of mitochondrial diseases that include: 1) childhood Myocerebrohepatopathy Spectrum disorders (MCHS) which include myopathy or hypotonia, dementia, and liver dysfunction; 2) Alpers syndrome also known as Alpers progressive infantile poliodystrophy; 3) Ataxia Neuropathy Spectrum (ANS) disorders; 4) Myoclonus Epilepsy Myopathy Sensory Ataxia (MEMSA); 5) Autosomal

recessive PEO (arPEO, which includes an overlapping spectrum of disorders like sensory ataxia, neuropathy, dysarthria, and ophthalmoplegia (SANDO), and 6) adPEO, 7) Parkinsonism, 8) Dementia, 9) liver dysfunction, 10) male infertility, etc. [28]. Furthermore, a mutation on *POLG1* gene in a homozygous state is the most common cause of AHS [30].

In this communication, both the mitochondrial replicative DNA pol γ (POLG1) and the nuclear-encoded RNA polymerase (NEP) from humans and various animals are analyzed for their polymerase and proofreading exonuclease domains and to identify the mitochondrial disease mutations in *POLG1* gene, which directly affect the functioning of the POLG1. Two of the critical dominant mutations, viz. R⁹⁴³→C/H and Y⁹⁵⁵→C/H, which are involved in many mitochondrial diseases in patients with a severe form of adPEO and severe, early-onset multi-systemic mitochondrial disease with bilateral sensorineural hearing loss, cataract, myopathy, and liver failure are identified in the polymerase catalytic site amino acids.

2. Materials and Methods

The protein sequence data of the mitochondrial DNA pol γ and NEP from various animal and human mitochondria were obtained from PUBMED and SWISS-PROT databases. The advanced version of Clustal Omega was used for protein sequence analysis. The polymerase and PR active sites are arrived at by sequence similarities, site-directed mutagenesis (SDM) and X-ray crystallographic data from DNA pol γ and other DNA and RNA polymerases already reported.

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 1 shows the MSA of the mitochondrial POLG1 from human and various animal sources. (Only the regions required for the discussions are shown here). The human sequence is used as the reference and highlighted in yellow. The N-terminal domain (NTD) of ~100 amino acids are not conserved and showed many gaps in the alignment, after that, conservations are observed and a clear demarcation of the PR exonuclease and DNA polymerase domains are observed, and marked by arrows. The linker region is found between them. Large number of consecutive Qs (polyQ tract) is common in some of the POLG1 sequences in the NTD and up to 13 of them are found in the human POLG1 sequence. Several inheritable neurodegenerative diseases, (also known as the polyglutamine diseases are monogenic and are the most common genetically inherited neurodegenerative disorders), occur due to abnormal expansion of the polyglutamine tract (CAG repeats), and the important examples of polyglutamine diseases are the spinocerebellar ataxia and Huntington's disease. A unique polybasic, K rich region – ⁴⁹⁶KQKKAKKVKK- and a **poly-E** motif (highlighted in human) are found in the linker region (Fig. 1) and its significance is not clear now.

The first completely conserved triad –D¹⁹⁸VE- of the DEDD-superfamily of exonucleases is seen after ~ 200 amino acids from the N-terminal. The PR exonuclease domain belongs to the subfamily DEDD(Y) and the active site amino acids are highlighted in light blue. The MSA analysis data are further confirmed by SDM analysis reported already [27] (Table 2). An SDM analysis of D¹⁹⁸→A, E²⁰⁰→A and D²⁷⁴→A of POLG1 exhibited no PR exonuclease activity [31, 32]. (Fig. 1).

The PR exonuclease domain is followed by the linker region. The linker region is implicated in the binding of the 55 kDa subunit. A large number of disease mutations are also found in the linker region. For example, Parkinsonism and ataxia, the most common movement disorders, are associated with POLG1 mutations in the highly conserved linker region (A⁴⁶⁷→T, S⁵¹¹→N, K⁵¹²→M and G⁵¹⁷→V) of POLG1 (Fig. 1). Among them the A⁴⁶⁷→T substitution is the most common. For example, the A⁴⁶⁷→T mutation is associated with a wide range of mitochondrial disorders, including Alpers syndrome (AS), juvenile spinocerebellar ataxia-epilepsy syndrome, and PEO, and each with vastly different clinical presentations, tissue specificities and ages of onset. On analysis, it was found that the A⁴⁶⁷→T mutant enzyme possesses only 4% of wild-type DNA polymerase activity, and the catalytic defect is manifested primarily through a 6-fold reduction in k_{cat} with minimal effect on exonuclease function [33, 34]. Very high frequencies (~36%) make the A⁴⁶⁷→T, the most common disease mutation of *POLG1* gene. Therefore, it is proposed that loss of accessory subunit interaction with POLG1 and reduced DNA polymerase activity are responsible for the depletion and deletion of mtDNA, observed in patients with the above diseases. Mutations in the gene for the catalytic subunit (POLG1) have been shown to be a frequent cause of many mitochondrial disorders. Nearly 50 disease causing mutations are located in the gene of the catalytic subunit of POLG1. Alpers' syndrome is a rare, heritable, fatal neurogenetic disorder that affects the brain and liver of young children. It is an autosomal recessive disease associated with mtDNA depletion disorder, characterized by refractory seizures, neurodegeneration, and liver disease. This is found to be due to deficiency in mitochondrial POLG1 catalytic activity. In two unrelated pedigrees of Alpers' syndrome, each affected child was found to carry a homozygous mutation in exon 17 of the *POLG1* gene locus that led to a Glu⁸⁷³→Stop mutation, just upstream of the polymerase catalytic core of the protein. In addition, each affected child was heterozygous for the mutation in exon 7 that led to an Ala⁴⁶⁷→Thr substitution in the POLG1 linker region (both are highlighted in magenta) [35].

The linker region is followed by the polymerase domain which is observed after ~750 amino acids and the proposed POLG1 catalytic site amino acids are highlighted in yellow (Fig. 1). The polymerase catalytic site, -S⁹⁴²R⁴EHA^{K947}I¹FNY⁹⁵¹GR⁹⁵³IY⁸G⁹⁵⁶A⁹⁵⁷- is found to be very similar to the already reported and confirmed active site of *E. coli* DNA pol I, -QR⁴RS^{A758}A¹¹INFLGIY⁸GM- [36] and in close agreement to the active sites of the other DNA/RNA polymerases already reported and suggesting high degree of evolutionary conservation among them (Table 3) [37]. Some of the *POLG1* catalytic site mutations have been found to be associated with autosomal recessive and dominant PEO (PEO is an autosomal mitochondrial disorder associated with depletion of the mitochondrial genome and/or the accumulation of mutations and deletions within mtDNA). Interestingly, it is found that the dominant *POLG1* mutations that are known to cause PEO are located within the polymerase domain and found in the amino acid substitutions of G⁹²³→D, R⁹⁴³→H, Y⁹⁵⁵→C and A⁹⁵⁷→S [31]. Ponamare et al., [38] found that a point mutation (Y⁹⁵⁵→C) in the DNA pol causes error-prone DNA synthesis in patients suffering from PEO. They found that this Y⁹⁵⁵→C version of the enzyme retained a wild-type catalytic rate, but suffered a 45-fold decrease in apparent binding affinity for the incoming NTPs. Furthermore, the error-prone DNA synthesis observed for the mutant Y⁹⁵⁵→C of *POLG1* is consistent with the accumulation of mitochondrial DNA mutations in patients with PEO. Similar observation was made by van Goethem et al., [39] with 3 generations of Belgian pedigree, with an autosomal, dominant PEO, where they identified a heterozygous mutation (Y⁹⁵⁵→C) in the polymerase motif B of the *POLG1*. Moreover, Lamantea, et al., [40] identified the heterozygous Y⁹⁵⁵→C mutation in 9 unrelated families with adPEO. Among them, 4 families were Italian and 1 was from Greece and 4 were Swedish families. MSA analysis has shown that the Y⁹⁵⁵ is the template-binding amino acid in the -Y⁹⁵⁵G- pair of the polymerase. Another mutation, viz. R⁹⁴³→H was found in patients with a severe form of adPEO [40]. R⁹⁴³ is critically important in binding the oxygen atoms of the γ-phosphate of the incoming dNTP and helps positioning it for catalysis [39, 40]. The mutant form of R⁹⁴³→H at this position causes again substantial loss of polymerase catalytic activity. For example, the recombinant protein expressing R⁹⁴³→H showed only 0.2% of wild-type polymerase activity *in vitro* [41]. Furthermore, the Y⁹⁵⁵ and R⁹⁴³ are highly conserved from yeasts to animals and humans (Fig. 1). MSA analysis has shown that the R⁹⁴³ is placed at -4 from the catalytic K as reported and confirmed as the amino acid involved in dNTP selection with *E. coli* DNA pol I. Mutations in the *POLG1* gene are also reported in breast cancer patients. Singh et al., [42] found that the *POLG1* gene was mutated in 63% of breast cancers and identified a total of 17 mutations across the *POLG1* gene. These mutations were found in all three domains of *POLG1* protein, including T²⁵¹→I (exonuclease domain), P⁵⁸⁷→L (linker region) and E¹¹⁴³→G (polymerase domain, highlighted in magenta).

The N- and C-terminals of the *POLG1* show putative zinc-binding motifs (ZBMs) (Fig. 2). Two invariant -DxD- type metal-binding motifs are found within the polymerase domain and highlighted in green and the -D⁸⁹⁰VD- and -HDE¹¹³⁶- are implicated in chelating two Mg²⁺ ions [28]. In addition to the PR exonuclease activity, the *POLG1* is also known to perform BER activity to remove oxidized bases and a (dRP)-lyase domain with the conserved amino acids from 353–391 is highlighted in grey. The lyase catalytic K³⁷¹ is marked in red [25] and interestingly, the BER domain is also found in the PR exonuclease region. The C-terminal domain is remarkably conserved in all with a highly conserved peptide (highlighted in grey).

CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) MSA of DNA polymerase γ from human and various animal sources.

tr A0A6J1VAB9 A0A6J1VAB9_9SAUR	-----SSSSAGLLLQEKTA	PVTGAPLQEEQRMNPLGI	-----	55					
sp P54099 DPOG1_MOUSE	-----MPSSENGQL	-----	RLNPLLI	59					
sp Q9QYV8 DPOG1_RAT	-----MPSSENGQL	-----	RLNPLHI	59					
tr A0A6P6HHU9 A0A6P6HHU9_PUMCO	-----ARFRCTGGVAAGS	WARPAGR--	APGRHCGCVPVGWATVRACV	104					
tr A0A2K5EPQ4 A0A2K5EPQ4_AOTNA	RQQPQ	-----	QQPPQVPSSEGGQL	-----	RHNPLHI	67			
tr F7IMR4 F7IMR4_CALJA	-	QQLQ	-----	QQPPQVPSSEGGQL	-----	RHNPLHI	66		
tr A0A2K5PBZ5 A0A2K5PBZ5_CEBIM	RQQPQ	-----	QQPPQVPSSEGGQL	-----	RHNPLHI	67			
tr A0A0D9RX64 A0A0D9RX64_CHLSB	RRQQQ	-----	LQQPQVPSSEGGQL	-----	RHNPLHI	66			
tr A0A2K6AY60 A0A2K6AY60_MACNE	RQQQQ	-----	LQQPQVPSSEGGQL	-----	RHNPLHI	66			
tr A0A2K5JYU3 A0A2K5JYU3_COLAP	RQQQLQ	-----	QQPQVPSSEGGQL	-----	RHNPLHI	67			
tr A0A2K6MGT5 A0A2K6MGT5_RHIBE	RRQQQQ	-----	QQPQVPSSEGGQL	-----	RHNPLHI	71			
tr A0A2J8VX21 A0A2J8VX21_PONAB	RRRQQ	-----	QQPQVPSSEGGQL	-----	RHNPLHI	72			
sp P54098 DPOG1_HUMAN	RRRQQQQQQQQQQ	QQPQVLSSEGGQL	-----	RHNPLDI	76				
tr G3R7U9 G3R7U9_GORGO	RRRQQQQQQQQ	QQPQVLSSEGGQL	-----	RHNPLDI	76				
tr A0A3Q7TNX2 A0A3Q7TNX2_VULVU	PQQQ	-----	QQPPPPARSSSEGGQL	-----	RHNPLHI	68			
tr A0A5F5XEZ4 A0A5F5XEZ4_FELCA	-	PPR	-----	PQQ	-----	VPSSEGGQQ	-----	RHNPLHI	63
tr M3WHT6 M3WHT6_FELCA	-	PPR	-----	PQQ	-----	VPSSEGGQQ	-----	RHNPLHI	63
tr A0A667FUI7 A0A667FUI7_LYNCA	-	PPR	-----	PQQ	-----	VPSSEGGQQ	-----	RHNPLHI	63
tr A0A8C8YBT2 A0A8C8YBT2_PANLE	PPPR	-----	PQQ	-----	VPSSEGGQQ	-----	RHNPLHI	64	
tr A0A7J8CKE5 A0A7J8CKE5_ROUAE	-	PP	-----	PPQPQVPSSEGGQP	-----	RYNPLHI	60		
tr A0A7J8CKI1 A0A7J8CKI1_ROUAE	-	PP	-----	PPQPQVPSSEGGQP	-----	RYNPLHI	60		
tr A0A5N3VIY8 A0A5N3VIY8_MUNMU	-	P	-----	PPPPVPSSEGGQL	-----	RHNPLHI	60		
tr A0A5N3X6N5 A0A5N3X6N5_MUNRE	-	P	-----	PPPPVPSSEGGQL	-----	RHNPLHI	60		
tr A0A8C2QXP3 A0A8C2QXP3_CAPHI	-	P	-----	PPPPVPSSEGGQL	-----	RHNPLHI	60		
tr A0A4W2GEN6 A0A4W2GEN6_BOBOX	-	P	-----	PSPQPVPSSVGGQL	-----	RHNPLHI	60		
tr E1BDI3 E1BDI3_BOVIN	-	P	-----	PSPQPVPSSVGGQL	-----	RHNPLHI	60		
tr A0A6B0QZX2 A0A6B0QZX2_9CETA	QP	-----	PSSEGGQL	-----	RHNPLHI	57			
tr A0A7J7FHZ9 A0A7J7FHZ9_DICBM	QPQ	-----	QQQVSSSEGGQL	-----	RHNPLHI	62			
tr A0A8B8S4S7 A0A8B8S4S7_CAMFR	QPQ	-----	QQQVSSSEGGQL	-----	RHNPLHI	62			
tr A0A340YA50 A0A340YA50_LIPVE	QPP	-----	PPPPVPSSEGGQL	-----	RHNPLHI	64			
tr A0A2Y9S364 A0A2Y9S364_PHYMC	-	Q	-----	PPVPSSEGGQL	-----	RHNPLHI	60		
tr A0A8B8WLT0 A0A8B8WLT0_BALMU	QPQ	-----	PPVPSSEGGQL	-----	RHNPLHI	62			

	NTD	PR Exo	
tr A0A6J1VAB9 A0A6J1VAB9_9SAUR	ANVDEHFRLLAQTSQSLP	YLEAAKELIEHEMPRPTEWAVEVGTQYGS DGEREKVDFPDE	171
sp P54099 DPOG1_MOUSE	GNLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAAAASLLEAQLPPEPKSWAWAEGWTRYGPEGEAEVPAIPEE	175
sp Q9QYV8 DPOG1_RAT	GNLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAAAASLSEAQLPPQPRKVVWAEAGWTRYGPEGEAEVPAIPEE	175
tr A0A6P6HHU9 A0A6P6HHU9_PUMCO	GSLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	HLLRRANQLLAGSACP-PPP XAWAEGWTRAWPHGGR-PHCIP E-	219
tr A0A2K5EPQ4 A0A2K5EPQ4_AOTNA	DNLDEHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLQQLPPQPPSWAWAEGWTRYGPEGEAEVPAIPEE	183
tr F7IMR4 F7IMR4_CALJA	DNLDEHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLQQLPPQPPSWAWAEGWTRYGPEGEAEVPAIPEE	182
tr A0A2K5PBZ5 A0A2K5PBZ5_CEBIM	DNLDEHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLQQLPPQPPSWAWAEGWTRYGPEGEAEVPAIPEE	183
tr A0A0D9RX64 A0A0D9RX64_CHLSB	DNLDEHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLQQLPPQPTGWAWAEGWTRYGPEGEAEVPAIPEE	182
tr A0A2K6AY60 A0A2K6AY60_MACNE	DNLDEHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLQQLPPQPTGWAWAEGWTRYGPEGEAEVPAIPEE	182
tr A0A2K5JYU3 A0A2K5JYU3_COLAP	DNLDEHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLQQLPPQPPGWAWAEGWTRYGPEGEAEVPAIPEE	183
tr A0A2K6MGT5 A0A2K6MGT5_RHIBE	DNLDEHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLQQLARLPQPPGWAWAEGWTRYGPEGEAEVPAIPEE	187
tr A0A2J8VX21 A0A2J8VX21_PONAB	DNLDEHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANLLLQQLPPKPPAWAWAEGWTRYGPEGEAEVPAIPEE	188
sp P54098 DPOG1_HUMAN	DNLDEHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANLLLQQLPPKPPAWAWAEGWTRYGPEGEAEVPAIPEE	192
tr G3R7U9 G3R7U9_GORGO	DNLDEHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANLLLQQLPPKPPAWAWAEGWTRYGPEGEAEVPAIPEE	192
tr A0A3Q7TNX2 A0A3Q7TNX2_VULVU	GSLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLRQQLPPRPPSWAWAEGWTRYGPEGEAEVPAIPEE	184
tr A0A5F5XEZ4 A0A5F5XEZ4_FELCA	GSLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLRRLP RP PPSWAWAEGWTRYGPAGEAEVPAIPEE	179
tr M3WHT6 M3WHT6_FELCA	GSLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLRRLP RP PPSWAWAEGWTRYGPAGEAEVPAIPEE	179
tr A0A667FUI7 A0A667FUI7_LYNCA	GSLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLRRLP RP PPSWAWAEGWTRYGPAGEAEVPAIPEE	179
tr A0A8C8YBT2 A0A8C8YBT2_PANLE	GSLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLRRLP RP PPSWAWAEGWTRYGPAGEAEVPAIPEE	180
tr A0A7J8CKE5 A0A7J8CKE5_ROUAE	GSLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLQQLP RP PPSWAWAEGWTRYGPAGEAEVPAIPEE	176
tr A0A7J8CKI1 A0A7J8CKI1_ROUAE	GSLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLQQLP RP PPSWAWAEGWTRYGPAGEAEVPAIPEE	176
tr A0A5N3VIY8 A0A5N3VIY8_MUNMU	GSLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLQQLP RP PPNWAWAEGWTRYGPAGEAEVPAIPEE	176
tr A0A5N3X6N5 A0A5N3X6N5_MUNRE	GSLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLQQLP RP PPNWAWAEGWTRYGPAGEAEVPAIPEE	176
tr A0A8C2QP3 A0A8C2QP3_CAPHI	GSLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLQQLP RP PPSWAWAEGWTRYGPAGEAEVPAIPEE	176
tr A0A4W2GEN6 A0A4W2GEN6_BOBOX	GSLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLQQLP RP PPSWAWAEGWTRYGPAGEAEVPAIPEE	176
tr E1BDI3 E1BDI3_BOVIN	GSLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLQQLP RP PPSWAWAEGWTRYGPAGEAEVPAIPEE	176
tr A0A6B0QZX2 A0A6B0QZX2_9CETA	GSLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLQQLP RP PPSWAWAEGWTRYGPAGEAEVPAIPEE	115
tr A0A7J7FHZ9 A0A7J7FHZ9_DICBM	GSLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANSLLQQLP RP PPSWAWAEGWTRYGPAGEAEVPAIPEE	173
tr A0A8B8S4S7 A0A8B8S4S7_CAMFR	GSLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANLLLQQLP RP PPSWAWAEGWTRYGPAGEAEVPAIPEE	178
tr A0A340YA50 A0A340YA50_LIPVE	GSLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANLLLQQLAP RP PPSWAWAEGWTRYGPAGEAEVPAIPEE	180
tr A0A2Y9S364 A0A2Y9S364_PHYMC	GSLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANLLLQQLAP RP PPSWAWAEGWTRYGPAGEAEVPAIPEE	176
tr A0A8B8WLT0 A0A8B8WLT0_BALMU	GSLDQHFRLLAQKQSLP	YLEAANLLLQQLAP RP PPNWAWAEGWTRYGPAGEAEVPAIPEE	178
..*:*** ***:**:*..:..*.*.*.*.*.***:.*:***			

tr A0A6J1VAB9 A0A6J1VAB9_9SAUR	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	228
sp P54099 DPOG1_MOUSE	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	232
sp Q9QYV8 DPOG1_RAT	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	232
tr A0A6P6HHU9 A0A6P6HHU9_PUMCO	EAPXFDVEVCLQREILPTLAVAXS SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	276
tr A0A2K5EPQ4 A0A2K5EPQ4_AOTNA	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	240
tr F7IMR4 F7IMR4_CALJA	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	239
tr A0A2K5PBZ5 A0A2K5PBZ5_CEBIM	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	240
tr A0A0D9RX64 A0A0D9RX64_CHLSB	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	239
tr A0A2K6AY60 A0A2K6AY60_MACNE	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	239
tr A0A2K5JYU3 A0A2K5JYU3_COLAP	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	240
tr A0A2K6MGT5 A0A2K6MGT5_RHIBE	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	244
tr A0A2J8VX21 A0A2J8VX21_PONAB	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	245
sp P54098 DPOG1_HUMAN	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	249
tr G3R7U9 G3R7U9_GORGO	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	249
tr A0A3Q7TNX2 A0A3Q7TNX2_VULVU	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	241
tr A0A5F5XEZ4 A0A5F5XEZ4_FELCA	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	236
tr M3WHT6 M3WHT6_FELCA	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	236
tr A0A667FUI7 A0A667FUI7_LYNCA	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	236
tr A0A8C8YBT2 A0A8C8YBT2_PANLE	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	237
tr A0A7J8CKE5 A0A7J8CKE5_ROUAE	QALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	233
tr A0A7J8CKI1 A0A7J8CKI1_ROUAE	QALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	233
tr A0A5N3VIY8 A0A5N3VIY8_MUNMU	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	233
tr A0A5N3X6N5 A0A5N3X6N5_MUNRE	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	233
tr A0A8C2QP3 A0A8C2QP3_CAPHI	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	233
tr A0A4W2GEN6 A0A4W2GEN6_BOBOX	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	233
tr E1BDI3 E1BDI3_BOVIN	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	233
tr A0A6B0QZX2 A0A6B0QZX2_9CETA	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	172
tr A0A7J7FHZ9 A0A7J7FHZ9_DICBM	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	230
tr A0A8B8S4S7 A0A8B8S4S7_CAMFR	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	235
tr A0A340YA50 A0A340YA50_LIPVE	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLXXXXEERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	240
tr A0A2Y9S364 A0A2Y9S364_PHYMC	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	233
tr A0A8B8WLT0 A0A8B8WLT0_BALMU	RALVE DVEVCLAEGTCTPLAVAI SPSAWYSWCS	BRRLV---EERYSWTSQSPADLIPLEV	235
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		← PR Exo →	Linker →	
tr A0A6J1VAB9 A0A6J1VAB9_9SAUR	KKEARELFIKGSMNDIRNNFQELMNYCALDQVQATYEIFHEQLP			LFLKRC PHPVTFAGMLE 405
sp P54099 DPOG1_MOUSE	EKEPRELFVKGSMRDIRENFQDLMOYCAFDVWATFEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 412
sp Q9QYV8 DPOG1_RAT	AKEPRELFVKGSMRDIRENFQDLMEYCAFDDVWATFEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 411
tr A0A6P6HHU9 A0A6P6HHU9_PUMCO	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDIREFQDLMOYCAQDVWATYEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 455
tr A0A2K5EPQ4 A0A2K5EPQ4_AOTNA	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDIREFQDLMOYCAQDVWATYEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 420
tr F7IMR4 F7IMR4_CALJA	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDIREFQDLMOYCAQDVWATHEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 419
tr A0A2K5PBZ5 A0A2K5PBZ5_CEBIM	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDIREFQDLMOYCAQDVWATHEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 420
tr A0A0D9RX64 A0A0D9RX64_CHLSB	EKEPRELFVKGTMKDIREFQDLMOYCAQDVWATHEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 418
tr A0A2K6AY60 A0A2K6AY60_MACNE	EKEPRELFVKGTMKDIREFQDLMOYCAQDVWATHEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 418
tr A0A2K5JYU3 A0A2K5JYU3_COLAP	EKEPRELFVKGTMKDIREFQDLMOYCAQDVWATHEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 420
tr A0A2K6MGT5 A0A2K6MGT5_RHIBE	EKEPRELFVKGTMKDIREFQDLMOYCAQDVWATHEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 424
tr A0A2J8VX21 A0A2J8VX21_PONAB	EKEPRELFVKGTMKDIREFQDLMOYCAQDVWATHEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 425
sp P54098 DPOG1_HUMAN	EKEPRELFVKGTMKDIREFQDLMOYCAQDVWATHEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 429
tr G3R7U9 G3R7U9_GORGO	EKEPRELFVKGTMKDIREFQDLMOYCAQDVWATHEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 429
tr A0A3Q7TNX2 A0A3Q7TNX2_VULVU	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDIREFQALMOYCAQDVWATYEIFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 420
tr A0A5F5XEZ4 A0A5F5XEZ4_FELCA	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDVRENFQDLMOYCAQDVWATYEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 415
tr M3WHT6 M3WHT6_FELCA	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDVRENFQDLMOYCAQDVWATYEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 415
tr A0A667FUI7 A0A667FUI7_LYNCA	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDVRENFQDLMOYCAQDVWATYEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 415
tr A0A8C8YBT2 A0A8C8YBT2_PANLE	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDVRENFQDLMOYCAQDVWATYEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 416
tr A0A7J8CKE5 A0A7J8CKE5_ROUAE	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDVRENFQDLMOYCAFDDVWATYEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 412
tr A0A7J8CKI1 A0A7J8CKI1_ROUAE	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDVRENFQDLMOYCAFDDVWATYEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 412
tr A0A5N3VIY8 A0A5N3VIY8_MUNMU	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDVRENFQDLMOYCAQDVWATYEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 412
tr A0A5N3X6N5 A0A5N3X6N5_MUNRE	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDVRENFQDLMOYCAQDVWATYEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 412
tr A0A8C2QXP3 A0A8C2QXP3_CAPHI	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDIREFQDLMOYCAQDVWATYEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 412
tr A0A4W2GEN6 A0A4W2GEN6_BOBOX	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDIREFQDLMOYCAQDAWATYEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 412
tr E1BDI3 E1BDI3_BOVIN	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDIREFQDLMOYCAQDAWATYEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 412
tr A0A6B0QZX2 A0A6B0QZX2_9CETA	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDIREFQDLMOYCAQDAWATYEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 351
tr A0A7J7FHZ9 A0A7J7FHZ9_DICBM	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDIREFQDLMOYCAQDVWATYEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 409
tr A0A8B8S4S7 A0A8B8S4S7_CAMFR	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDIREFQDLMOYCAQDVWATYEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 414
tr A0A340YA50 A0A340YA50_LIPVE	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDIREFQDLMOYCAQDVWATYEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 419
tr A0A2Y9S364 A0A2Y9S364_PHYMC	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDIREFQDLMOYCAQDVWATYEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 412
tr A0A8B8WLT0 A0A8B8WLT0_BALMU	EKEPRELFVKGSMKDIREFQDLMOYCAQDVWATYEVFQQQLP			LFLERC PHPVTLAGMLE 414
	** ** ** ** **			** ** ** **

tr A0A6J1VAB9 A0A6J1VAB9_9SAUR	MGVSYLPVNQNWYKYLDEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMNLADDAQQLI	HHERYKDDPWWDLK	465
sp P54099 DPOG1_MOUSE	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	472
sp Q9QYV8 DPOG1_RAT	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMELANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	471
tr A0A6P6HHU9 A0A6P6HHU9_PUMCO	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLADDAQQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	515
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tr F7IMR4 F7IMR4_CALJA	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLVEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	479
tr A0A2K5PBZ5 A0A2K5PBZ5_CEBIM	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLVEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	480
tr A0A0D9RX64 A0A0D9RX64_CHLSB	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	478
tr A0A2K6AY60 A0A2K6AY60_MACNE	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	478
tr A0A2K5JYU3 A0A2K5JYU3_COLAP	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	480
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tr A0A2J8VX21 A0A2J8VX21_PONAB	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLSEAQGTVEELQREMKKSLMDLANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	485
sp P54098 DPOG1_HUMAN	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	AS 489
tr G3R7U9 G3R7U9_GORGO	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	489
tr A0A3Q7TNX2 A0A3Q7TNX2_VULVU	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	480
tr A0A5F5XEZ4 A0A5F5XEZ4_FELCA	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLADDAQQLI	SGERYKDDPWLWDL	475
tr M3WHT6 M3WHT6_FELCA	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLADDAQQLI	SGERYKDDPWLWDL	475
tr A0A667FUI7 A0A667FUI7_LYNCA	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLADDAQQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	475
tr A0A8C8YBT2 A0A8C8YBT2_PANLE	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLADDAQQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	476
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tr A0A7J8CKI1 A0A7J8CKI1_ROUAE	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	472
tr A0A5N3VIY8 A0A5N3VIY8_MUNMU	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	472
tr A0A5N3X6N5 A0A5N3X6N5_MUNRE	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	472
tr A0A8C2QXP3 A0A8C2QXP3_CAPHI	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	472
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tr E1BDI3 E1BDI3_BOVIN	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	472
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tr A0A7J7FHZ9 A0A7J7FHZ9_DICBM	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	469
tr A0A8B8S4S7 A0A8B8S4S7_CAMFR	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	474
tr A0A340YA50 A0A340YA50_LIPVE	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	479
tr A0A2Y9S364 A0A2Y9S364_PHYMC	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	472
tr A0A8B8WLT0 A0A8B8WLT0_BALMU	MGVSYLPVNQNWERYLLEAQTVEELQREMKKSLMDLANDACQLI	SGERYKEDPWLWDL	474
	*****	*****	*****

tr A0A6J1VAB9 A0A6J1VAB9_9SAUR	WDLQNFQKQKTKPTRKKKEGANEEESP-KVVGKASPPPEWQEDPGPPEEEEEQSQNG--RQQV	522
sp P54099 DPOG1_MOUSE	WDLQEFKQKKAkkvK--KPASASKLPIEGAGPFGDPMQEDPGPPEEEEELQRSVTAHNR	530
sp Q9QYV8 DPOG1_RAT	WDLQEFKQKKAkkvK--KTASASKLPIEGAGPFGDPMQEDPGPPEEEEELQONIMAHTR	529
tr A0A6P6HHU9 A0A6P6HHU9_PUMCO	WGLQEFKQKVKQVQRKEPVAASQLPTEGAGAPGDPKQEDPGPPEEEEEAQRDVTARAC	575
tr A0A2K5EPQ4 A0A2K5EPQ4_AOTNA	WDLQEFKQKARKVK-KEPATASKLPIEGGAPGDPMDERDLAPPSEEEEEFQQDVAARAC	539
tr F7IMR4 F7IMR4_CALJA	WDLQEFKQKARKVK-KEPATASKLPIEGGAPGDPMDQEDLGPPEEEEEFQQDVAARAC	538
tr A0A2K5PBZ5 A0A2K5PBZ5_CEBIM	WDLQEFKQKARKVK-KEPATASKLPIEGTAPGDPMDQEDLGPPEEEEEFQQDVAARAC	539
tr A0A0D9RX64 A0A0D9RX64_CHLSB	WDLQEFKQKARKVK-KELATASKLPIEGAGAPGDPMDQEDLGPPEEEEEFQQDVMARAC	537
tr A0A2K6AY60 A0A2K6AY60_MACNE	WDLQEFKQKARKVK-KEPATASKLPIEGAGAPGDPMDQEDLGPPEEEEEFQQDVMARAC	537
tr A0A2K5JYU3 A0A2K5JYU3_COLAP	WDLQEFKQKARKVK-KEPATASKLPIEGAGAPGDPMDQEDLGPPEEEEEFQQDVMARAC	539
tr A0A2K6MGT5 A0A2K6MGT5_RHIBE	WDLQEFKQKARKVK-KEPATASKLPIEGAGAPGDPMDQEDLGPPEEEEEFQQDVMARAC	543
tr A0A2J8VX21 A0A2J8VX21_PONAB	WDLQEFKQKARKVK-KEPATASKLPIEGAGAPGDPMDQEDLGPPEEEEEFQQDVMARAC	544
sp P54098 DPOG1_HUMAN	WDLQEFKQKKAkkvK-KEPATASKLPIEGAGAPGDPMDQEDLGPPEEEEEFQQDVMARAC	548
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tr A0A5F5XEZ4 A0A5F5XEZ4_FELCA	WGLQEFKQKVKQVQRKEPVAASQLPTEGAGAPGDPKQEDPGPPEEEEEARRDVTARAC	535
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tr A0A8B8S4S7 A0A8B8S4S7_CAMFR	WDLQEFKQKARKVKRKEPAASKLPVEGAGAPGDPKQEDPGPPEEEEEFQRDVTARAC	534
tr A0A340YA50 A0A340YA50_LIPVE	WDLQEFKQKARKVKTKEPAAASKLPVEGPKAPGDPKQEDPGPPEEEEEQRDVMARAC	539
tr A0A2Y9S364 A0A2Y9S364_PHYMC	WDLQEFKQKARKVKTKEPAAASKLPVEGPEAPGDPKQEDPGPPEEEEEQRDVMARAC	532
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sp P54099 DPOG1_MOUSE	KSSQPTYHHGNGPYNDVNI PGCWFFKLPKHKDGNNYNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 764
sp Q9QYV8 DPOG1_RAT	KTSQPTYHHGNGPYNDVNI PGCWFFKLPKHKDGNNYNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 762
tr A0A6P6HHU9 A0A6P6HHU9_PUMCO	RASQPAYHHGNGPYNDVDV PGCWFFKLPKHKDGS SFNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 812
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tr F7IMR4 F7IMR4_CALJA	KDSQPTYHHGNGPYNDVDV PGCWFFKLPKHKDGNNYNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 775
tr A0A2K5PBZ5 A0A2K5PBZ5_CEBIM	KDSQPTYHHGNGPYNDVDV PGCWFFKLPKHKDGNNYNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 776
tr A0A0D9RX64 A0A0D9RX64_CHLSB	KDSQPNYHHGNGPYNDVDI PGCWFFKLPKHKDGN SCNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 774
tr A0A2K6AY60 A0A2K6AY60_MACNE	KDSQPNYHHGNGPYNDVDI PGCWFFKLPKHKDGN SCNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 774
tr A0A2K5JYU3 A0A2K5JYU3_COLAP	KDSQPNYHHGNGPYNDVDI PGCWFFKLPKHKDGN SCNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 776
tr A0A2K6MGT5 A0A2K6MGT5_RHIBE	KDSQPNYHHGNGPYNDVDI PGCWFFKLPKHKDGN SCNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 780
tr A0A2J8VX21 A0A2J8VX21_PONAB	KDTQPSYHHGNGPYNDVDI PGCWFFKLPKHKDGN SCNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 781
sp P54098 DPOG1_HUMAN	KDTQPSYHHGNGPYNDVDI PGCWFFKLPKHKDGN SCNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 785
tr G3R7U9 G3R7U9_GORGO	KDTQPSYHHGNGPYNDVDI PGCWFFKLPKHKDGN SCNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 785
tr A0A3Q7TNX2 A0A3Q7TNX2_VULVU	RASQPAYHHGNGPYNDVDI PGCWFFKLPKHKDGGC NVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 776
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tr M3WHT6 M3WHT6_FELCA	RASQPAYHHGNGPYNDVDV PGCWFFKLPKHKDGS SFNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 772
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tr A0A8C8YBT2 A0A8C8YBT2_PANLE	RASQPAYHHGNGPYNDVDV PGCWFFKLPKHKDGS SFNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 773
tr A0A7J8CKE5 A0A7J8CKE5_ROUAE	KASQPAYHHGSGPYNDVDI PGCWFFKLPKHKDGN NFNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 769
tr A0A7J8CKI1 A0A7J8CKI1_ROUAE	KASQPAYHHGSGPYNDVDI PGCWFFKLPKHKDGN NFNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 769
tr A0A5N3VIY8 A0A5N3VIY8_MUNMU	KASQPAYHHGNGPYNDVDI PGCWFFKLPKHKDGS SCNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 769
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tr A0A8C2QXP3 A0A8C2QXP3_CAPHI	KASQPAYHHGNGPYNDVDI PGCWFFKLPKHKDGN SCNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 769
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tr A0A7J7FHZ9 A0A7J7FHZ9_DICBM	KASQPAYHHGNGPYNDVDI PGCWFFKLPKHKDGN SCNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 766
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tr A0A340YA50 A0A340YA50_LIPVE	KASQPAYHHGNGPYNDVDI PGCWFFKLPKHKDGN SCNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 776
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tr A0A8B8WLT0 A0A8B8WLT0_BALMU	KASQPAYHHGNGPYNDVDI PGCWFFKLPKHKDGN SCNVGSP	FAKDFLPKMEDGTLQAGPGG 771

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sp P54099 DPOG1_MOUSE	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRVTRHPAFDEEGHYGAILPQVV	824
sp Q9QYV8 DPOG1_RAT	ARGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPSPFDEESHYGAILPQVV	822
tr A0A6P6HHU9 A0A6P6HHU9_PUMCO	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPRYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	872
tr A0A2K5EPQ4 A0A2K5EPQ4_AOTNA	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPDYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	836
tr F7IMR4 F7IMR4_CALJA	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPDYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	835
tr A0A2K5PBZ5 A0A2K5PBZ5_CEBIM	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPDYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	836
tr A0A0D9RX64 A0A0D9RX64_CHLSB	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPDYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	834
tr A0A2K6AY60 A0A2K6AY60_MACNE	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPDYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	834
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tr A0A2K6MGT5 A0A2K6MGT5_RHIBE	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPDYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	840
tr A0A2J8VX21 A0A2J8VX21_PONAB	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPDYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	841
sp P54098 DPOG1_HUMAN	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPDYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	845
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tr A0A3Q7TNX2 A0A3Q7TNX2_VULVU	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPDYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	836
tr A0A5F5XEZ4 A0A5F5XEZ4_FELCA	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPRYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	832
tr M3WHT6 M3WHT6_FELCA	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPRYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	832
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tr A0A7J8CKI1 A0A7J8CKI1_ROUAE	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPDYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	829
tr A0A5N3VIY8 A0A5N3VIY8_MUNMU	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPDYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	829
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tr A0A8C2QXP3 A0A8C2QXP3_CAPHI	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPDYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	829
tr A0A4W2GEN6 A0A4W2GEN6_BOBOX	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPDYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	829
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tr A0A7J7FHZ9 A0A7J7FHZ9_DICBM	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPDYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	826
tr A0A8B8S4S7 A0A8B8S4S7_CAMFR	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPDYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	831
tr A0A340YA50 A0A340YA50_LIPVE	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPDYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	836
tr A0A2Y9S364 A0A2Y9S364_PHYMC	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPDYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	829
tr A0A8B8WLT0 A0A8B8WLT0_BALMU	ASGERALEINKMISFWRNAHKRISSQMVVWLPRESALPRAVTRHPDYDEEGHYGAILPQVV	831
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tr F7IMR4 F7IMR4_CALJA	TAGTITRRAVEPTWLTASNARPDVRSSELKAMVQAPPGYVHVGADVDSQELWIAAVLGEA	895
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tr A0A2J8VX21 A0A2J8VX21_PONAB	TAGTITRRAVEPTWLTASNARPDVRSSELKAMVQAPPGYVHVGADVDSQELWIAAVLGEA	901
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tr A0A5F5XEZ4 A0A5F5XEZ4_FELCA	TAGTITRRAVEPTWLTASNARPDVRSSELKAMVQAPPGYVHVGADVDSQELWIAAVLGEA	892
tr M3WHT6 M3WHT6_FELCA	TAGTITRRAVEPTWLTASNARPDVRSSELKAMVQAPPGYVHVGADVDSQELWIAAVLGEA	892
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tr A0A8C2QXP3 A0A8C2QXP3_CAPHI	TAGTITRRAVEPTWLTASNARPDVRSSELKAMVQAPPGYVHVGADVDSQELWIAAVLGEA	889
tr A0A4W2GEN6 A0A4W2GEN6_BOBOX	TAGTITRRAVEPTWLTASNARPDVRSSELKAMVQAPPGYVHVGADVDSQELWIAAVLGEA	889
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tr A0A8B8S4S7 A0A8B8S4S7_CAMFR	TAGTITRRAVEPTWLTASNARPDVRSSELKAMVQAPPGYVHVGADVDSQELWIAAVLGEA	891
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tr A0A8B8WLT0 A0A8B8WLT0_BALMU	TAGTITRRAVEPTWLTASNARPDVRSSELKAMVQAPPGYVHVGADVDSQELWIAAVLGEA	891
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tr A0A6J1VAB9 A0A6J1VAB9_9SAUR	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSNNTDLHSTASTVGI	REHAKVFN	YGR	IYAGQ	FAERL	926
sp P54099 DPOG1_MOUSE	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTAAATVGI	REHAKIFN	YGR	IYAGQ	SFAERL	944
sp Q9QYV8 DPOG1_RAT	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTAAATVGI	REHAKVFN	YGR	IYAGQ	SFAERL	942
tr A0A6P6HHU9 A0A6P6HHU9_PUMCO	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTASTVGI	REHAKIFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	992
tr A0A2K5EPQ4 A0A2K5EPQ4_AOTNA	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTASTVGI	REHAKVFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	956
tr F7IMR4 F7IMR4_CALJA	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTASTVGI	REHAKVFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	955
tr A0A2K5PBZ5 A0A2K5PBZ5_CEBIM	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTASTVGI	REHAKVFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	956
tr A0A0D9RX64 A0A0D9RX64_CHLSB	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTASTVGI	REHAKVFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	954
tr A0A2K6AY60 A0A2K6AY60_MACNE	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTASTVGI	REHAKVFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	954
tr A0A2K5JYU3 A0A2K5JYU3_COLAP	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTASTVGI	REHAKVFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	956
tr A0A2K6MGT5 A0A2K6MGT5_RHIBE	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTAAATVGI	REHAKVFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	960
tr A0A2J8VX21 A0A2J8VX21_PONAB	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTASTVGI	REHAKIFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	961
sp P54098 DPOG1_HUMAN	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTASTVGI	REHAKIFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	965
tr G3R7U9 G3R7U9_GORGO	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTASTVGI	REHAKIFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	965
tr A0A3Q7TNX2 A0A3Q7TNX2_VULVU	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTAAATVGI	REHAKIFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	956
tr A0A5F5XEZ4 A0A5F5XEZ4_FELCA	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTASTVGI	REHAKIFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	952
tr M3WHT6 M3WHT6_FELCA	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTASTVGI	REHAKIFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	952
tr A0A667FUI7 A0A667FUI7_LYNCA	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTASTVGI	REHAKIFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	952
tr A0A8C8YBT2 A0A8C8YBT2_PANLE	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTASTVGI	REHAKIFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	953
tr A0A7J8CKE5 A0A7J8CKE5_ROUAE	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTAAATVGI	REHAKVFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	949
tr A0A7J8CKI1 A0A7J8CKI1_ROUAE	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTAAATVGI	REHAKVFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	949
tr A0A5N3VIY8 A0A5N3VIY8_MUNMU	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTAAATVGI	REHAKIFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	949
tr A0A5N3X6N5 A0A5N3X6N5_MUNRE	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTAAATVGI	REHAKIFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	949
tr A0A8C2QXP3 A0A8C2QXP3_CAPHI	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTAAATVGI	REHAKIFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	949
tr A0A4W2GEN6 A0A4W2GEN6_BOBOX	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTAAATVGI	REHAKIFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	949
tr E1BDI3 E1BDI3_BOVIN	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTAAATVGI	REHAKIFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	949
tr A0A6B0QZX2 A0A6B0QZX2_9CETA	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTAAATVGI	REHAKIFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	888
tr A0A7J7FHZ9 A0A7J7FHZ9_DICBM	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTAAATVGI	REHAKIFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	946
tr A0A8B8S4S7 A0A8B8S4S7_CAMFR	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTAAATVGI	REHAKVFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	951
tr A0A340YA50 A0A340YA50_LIPVE	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTAAATVGI	REHAKVFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	956
tr A0A2Y9S364 A0A2Y9S364_PHYMC	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTAAATVGI	REHAKVFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	949
tr A0A8B8WLT0 A0A8B8WLT0_BALMU	HFAGMHGCTAFGWMTLQGRKSRGTDLHSTAAATVGI	REHAKVFN	YGR	IYAGQ	PFAERL	951
*****:*. .*****:*****:*****:***** *****						

tr A0A6J1VAB9 A0A6J1VAB9_9SAUR	WRLQREAKKRSRKKWDMVRQVWASGTESEMFNKLES	IAMS	DAPST	PVLGCR	ISRALEP	1046
sp P54099 DPOG1_MOUSE	RMIRREASRKS	RWKKWEV	AAERAWT	GGTESEMFNKLES	IAMSDTPRTPVLGCCISRALEP	1064
sp Q9QYV8 DPOG1_RAT	RKIRREASRKS	RWKKWEV	VTERAWT	GGTESEMFNKLES	IAMSDTPRTPVLGCCISRALEP	1062
tr A0A6P6HHU9 A0A6P6HHU9_PUMCO	RKIQREASRKS	HWKKWEV	VAERAWM	GGTESEMFNKLES	IATSDTPCTPVLGCRISRALEP	1112
tr A0A2K5EPQ4 A0A2K5EPQ4_AOTNA	RKVQREASRKS	RWKKWEV	VAERAWM	GGTESEMFNKLES	IATSDIPRTPVLGCRISRALEP	1076
tr F7IMR4 F7IMR4_CALJA	RKVQREASRKS	RWKKWEV	VAERAWM	GGTESEMFNKLES	IATSDIPCTPVLGCRISRALEP	1075
tr A0A2K5PBZ5 A0A2K5PBZ5_CEBIM	RKVQRETARKS	RWKKWEV	VAERAWM	GGTESEMFNKLES	IATSDIPRTPVLGCRISRALEP	1076
tr A0A0D9RX64 A0A0D9RX64_CHLSB	RKVQRETARKS	HWKKWEV	IAERAWK	GGTESEMFNKLES	IATSDIPRTPVLGCRISRALEP	1074
tr A0A2K6AY60 A0A2K6AY60_MACNE	RKVQREARKS	HWKKWEV	IAERAWK	GGTESEMFNKLES	IATSDIPRTPVLGCRISRALEP	1074
tr A0A2K5JYU3 A0A2K5JYU3_COLAP	RKVQRETARKS	HWKKWEV	VAERAWK	GGTESEMFNKLES	IATSDIPRTPVLGCRISRALEP	1076
tr A0A2K6MGT5 A0A2K6MGT5_RHIBE	RKVQRETARKS	RWKKWEV	VAERAWK	GGTESEMFNKLES	IATSDIPRTPVLGCRISRALEP	1080
tr A0A2J8VX21 A0A2J8VX21_PONAB	RKVQRETARKS	QWKKWEV	IAERAWK	GGTESEMFNKLES	IATSDIPRTPVLGCRISRALEP	1081
sp P54098 DPOG1_HUMAN	RKVQRETARKS	QWKKWEV	VAERAWK	GGTESEMFNKLES	IATSDIPRTPVLGCCISRALEP	1085
tr G3R7U9 G3R7U9_GORGO	RKVQRETARKS	QWKKWEV	VAERAWK	GGTESEMFNKLES	IATSDIPRTPVLGCRISRALEP	1085
tr A0A3Q7TNX2 A0A3Q7TNX2_VULVU	-----RSR	WKKWEV	VAERAWR	GGTESEMFNKLES	IAMSDTPCTPVLGCRISRALEP	1035
tr A0A5F5XEZ4 A0A5F5XEZ4_FELCA	-----RSH	WKKWEV	VAERAWM	GGTESEMFNKLES	IATSDTPRTPVLGCRISRALEP	1031
tr M3WHT6 M3WHT6_FELCA	RKIQREASRKS	HWKKWEV	VAERAWM	GGTESEMFNKLES	IATSDTPRTPVLGCRISRALEP	1072
tr A0A667FUI7 A0A667FUI7_LYNCA	RKIQREASRKS	HWKKWEV	VAERAWM	GGTESEMFNKLES	IATSDTPCTPVLGCRISRALEP	1072
tr A0A8C8YBT2 A0A8C8YBT2_PANLE	RKIQREASRKS	HWKKWEV	VAERAWM	GGTESEMFNKLES	IATSDTPCTPVLGCRISRALEP	1073
tr A0A7J8CKE5 A0A7J8CKE5_ROUAE	-----SR	WKKWEV	VAERAWM	GGTESEMFNKLES	IAMSDTPRTPVLGCRISRALEP	1028
tr A0A7J8CKI1 A0A7J8CKI1_ROUAE	RKIQREASRKS	RWKKWEV	VAERAWM	GGTESEMFNKLES	IAMSDTPCTPVLGCRISRALEP	1069
tr A0A5N3VIY8 A0A5N3VIY8_MUNMU	RRIQREASRKS	RWKKWEV	VAERAWM	GGTESEMFNKLENI	IATSDIPRTPVLGCRISRALEP	1069
tr A0A5N3X6N5 A0A5N3X6N5_MUNRE	RRIQREASRKS	RWKKWEV	VAERAWM	GGTESEMFNKLENI	IATSDIPRTPVLGCCISRALEP	1069
tr A0A8C2QXP3 A0A8C2QXP3_CAPHI	RKIQREASRKS	RWKKWEV	VAERAWI	GGTESEMFNKLES	IATSDIPSTPVLGCRISRALEP	1069
tr A0A4W2GEN6 A0A4W2GEN6_BOBOX	RKIQREASRKS	RWKKWEV	VQRAWM	GGTESEMFNKLES	IATSDIPRTPVLGCRISRALEP	1069
tr E1BDI3 E1BDI3_BOVIN	RKIQREASRKS	RWKKWEV	VQRAWM	GGTESEMFNKLES	IATSDIPRTPVLGCRISRALEP	1069
tr A0A6B0QZX2 A0A6B0QZX2_9CETA	RKIQREASRKS	RWKKWEV	VQRAWM	GGTESEMFNKLES	IATSDIPCTPVLGCRISRALEP	1008
tr A0A7J7FHZ9 A0A7J7FHZ9_DICBM	RKIQREASRKS	RWKKWEV	VAERAWM	GGTESEMFNKLES	IATSDTPCTPVLGCRISRALEP	1066
tr A0A8B8S4S7 A0A8B8S4S7_CAMFR	RKIQREASRKS	RWKKWEV	VAERAWM	GGTESEMFNKLES	IAMSDTPRTPVLGCRISRALEP	1071
tr A0A340YA50 A0A340YA50_LIPVE	RKIQREASRKS	QWKKWEV	VAERAWM	GGTESEMFNKLES	IAMSDTPRTPVLGCRITRALEP	1076
tr A0A2Y9S364 A0A2Y9S364_PHYMC	RKIQREASRKS	QWKKWEV	VAERAWM	GGTESEMFNKLES	IAMSDTPRTPVLGCRITRALEP	1069
tr A0A8B8WLT0 A0A8B8WLT0_BALMU	-----RS	QWKKWEV	VAERAWM	GGTESEMFNKLES	IAMSDTPRTPVLGCRITRALEP	1030
: :: :*. * *****.* ** * ***** *:*****						

//End of pol γ sequences

tr A0A6J1VAB9 A0A6J1VAB9_9SAUR	LEQSYNVSQGEALDIYKLIQITKGSLEK	GK-----	1196
sp P54099 DPOG1_MOUSE	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	RSQPGF----	1218
sp Q9QYV8 DPOG1_RAT	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	RSQPGF----	1216
tr A0A6P6HHU9 A0A6P6HHU9_PUMCO	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	-----	1260
tr A0A2K5EPQ4 A0A2K5EPQ4_AOTNA	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	RSQPGF----	1230
tr F7IMR4 F7IMR4_CALJA	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	RSQPGF----	1229
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tr A0A2K6MGT5 A0A2K6MGT5_RHIBE	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	RSQPGF----	1234
tr A0A2J8VX21 A0A2J8VX21_PONAB	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	RSQPGF----	1235
sp P54098 DPOG1_HUMAN	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	RSQPGF----	1239
tr G3R7U9 G3R7U9_GORGO	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	RSQPGF----	1239
tr A0A3Q7TNX2 A0A3Q7TNX2_VULVU	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	-----	1183
tr A0A5F5XEZ4 A0A5F5XEZ4_FELCA	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	-----	1179
tr M3WHT6 M3WHT6_FELCA	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	-----	1220
tr A0A667FUI7 A0A667FUI7_LYNCA	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	-----	1220
tr A0A8C8YBT2 A0A8C8YBT2_PANLE	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	S-PPGF----	1226
tr A0A7J8CKE5 A0A7J8CKE5_ROUAE	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	-----	1176
tr A0A7J8CKI1 A0A7J8CKI1_ROUAE	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	-----	1217
tr A0A5N3VIY8 A0A5N3VIY8_MUNMU	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	-----	1217
tr A0A5N3X6N5 A0A5N3X6N5_MUNRE	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	-----	1217
tr A0A8C2QXP3 A0A8C2QXP3_CAPHI	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	-----	1217
tr A0A4W2GEN6 A0A4W2GEN6_BOBOX	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	-----	1217
tr E1BDI3 E1BDI3_BOVIN	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	-----	1217
tr A0A6B0QZX2 A0A6B0QZX2_9CETA	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	-----	1156
tr A0A7J7FHZ9 A0A7J7FHZ9_DICBM	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	RSQPGF----	1220
tr A0A8B8S4S7 A0A8B8S4S7_CAMFR	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	RSQPGF----	1225
tr A0A340YA50 A0A340YA50_LIPVE	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	RSQPGF----	1230
tr A0A2Y9S364 A0A2Y9S364_PHYMC	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	-----	1217
tr A0A8B8WLT0 A0A8B8WLT0_BALMU	MERRYGIPOGEALDIYQIIELTKGSLEK	-----	1178

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Figure 1 MSA of mitochondrial DNA polymerase γ from human and various animal sources AS, Alper’s syndrome; BC, Breast cancer; Mutations in the polymerase region are shown in magenta

A0A6J1VAB9_9SAUR	<i>Notechis scutatus</i> (Snake)	P54099 DPOG1_MOUSE	<i>Mus musculus</i> (Mouse)
Q9QYV8 DPOG1_RAT	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i> (Rat)	A0A6P6HHU9_PUMCO	<i>Puma concolor</i> (Panther)
A0A2K5EPQ4_AOTNA	<i>Aotus nancymaae</i> (Monkey)	F7IMR4_CALJA	<i>Callithrix jacchus</i> (Monkey)
A0A2K5PBZ5_CEBIM	<i>Cebus imitator</i> (Capuchin)	A0A0D9RX64_CHLSB	<i>Chlorocebus sabaenus</i> (Monkey)
A0A2K6AY60_MACNE	<i>Macaca nemestrina</i> (Macaque)	A0A2K5JYU3_COLAP	<i>Colobus angolensis palliatus</i>
A0A2K6MGT5_RHIBE	<i>Rhinopithecus bieti</i> (Monkey)	A0A2J8VX21_PONAB	<i>Pongo abelii</i> (Orangutan)
P54098 DPOG1_HUMAN	<i>Homo sapiens</i> (Human)	G3R7U9_GORGO	<i>Gorilla gorilla</i> (Gorilla)
A0A3Q7TNX2_VULVU	<i>Vulpes vulpes</i> (Red fox)	A0A5F5XEZ4_FELCA	<i>Felis catus</i> (Cat)
M3WHT6_FELCA	<i>Felis catus</i> (Cat)	A0A667FUI7_LYNCA	<i>Lynx Canadensis</i> (Cat family)
A0A8C8YBT2_PANLE	<i>Panthera leo</i> (Lion)	A0A7J8CKE5_ROUAE	<i>Rousettus aegyptiacus</i> (Fruit bat)
A0A7J8CKI1_ROUAE	<i>Rousettus aegyptiacus</i> (Fruit bat)	A0A5N3VIY8_MUNMU	<i>Muntiacus muntjak</i> (Asian Deer)
A0A5N3X6N5_MUNRE	<i>Muntiacus reevesi</i> (Deer family)	A0A8C2QXP3_CAPHI	<i>Capra hircus</i> (Goat)
A0A4W2GEN6_BOBOX	<i>Bos indicus/ Taurus</i>	E1BDI3_BOVIN	<i>Bos Taurus</i> (Bovine)
A0A6B0QZX2_9CETA	<i>Bos mutus</i> (Wild yak)	A0A7J7FHZ9_DICBM	<i>Diceros bicornis</i> (Rhinoceros)
A0A8B8S4S7_CAMFR	<i>Camelus ferus</i> (Camel)	A0A340YA50_LIPVE	<i>Lipotes vexillifer</i> (River dolphin)
A0A2Y9S364_PHYMC	<i>Physeter macrocephalus</i> (Whale)	A0A8B8WLT0_BALMU	<i>Balaenoptera musculus</i> (Blue whale)

In addition to the replication and repair functions, the POLG1 is also found to play an important role in embryo development. Hance et al., [43] demonstrated that POLG1 deficiency in mouse embryos caused an early developmental arrest between embryonic days 7.5 and 8.5 and was found associated with severe mtDNA depletion. Therefore, they concluded that the presence of intact POLG1 is absolutely essential for the organogenesis during mammalian embryonic development.

Figure 2 shows the proposed organization of the various domains of the human mitochondrial POLG1, plant Chloroplast/Mitochondria DNA pols IA and IB from *A. thaliana* and *E. coli* DNA pol I. Even though the N-terminal region of ~125 amino acids is not conserved in POLG1 from human and animals, the C-terminal region is highly conserved. In contrast to *E. coli* and plant enzymes, in the human and animal mitochondrial POLG1, the PR exonuclease and the polymerase domains are connected by a linker. The linker region is something special found in the human/animal mitochondrial POLG1 and it essentially interacts with the 55 kDa, the second subunit of the enzyme (other two are monomeric, SSU enzymes). The polymerase and the PR exonuclease regions of the human POLG1 show putative ZBMs

(highlighted in orange). Defects of mitochondrial polymerase POLG1 underlie wide range of human diseases like dementia, Parkinsonism, ataxia, retinopathy, cataract, cardiomyopathy, liver failure, deafness, diabetes, infantile Alpers syndrome, etc. as discussed elsewhere. It should be noted that nearly all of the adPEO mutations in human *POLG1* gene are located in the polymerase catalytic region. To date, it is found that the vast majority of dominant mutations are in the polymerase domain of *POLG1* with a few exceptions like the A⁴⁶⁷→T in the linker region of the protein. The polymerase and the PR exonuclease regions of the human POLG1 show putative ZBMs (highlighted in orange).

NTD, N-terminal domain; PR exo, 3'-5' DEDD-superfamily of exonuclease domain; ZBM, Zinc-binding motif; Pol, Polymerase domain. DNA repair exo, 5'-3' exonuclease.

Figure 2 Comparison of the three closely related pols: 1) Human Mitochondrial POLG1; 2) Mitochondrial/Chloroplast DNA pols IA & IB from *A. thaliana* and 3) *E. coli* DNA pol I

Figure 3 shows the 'Mix and Match' MSA analysis of human mitochondrial POLG1, plant mitochondrial/chloroplast DNA pols IA and IB, and *E. coli* DNA pol I (only the regions required for the discussion are shown here). The catalytic core is highly conserved in all the four DNA polymerases and the completely conserved catalytic amino acids are aligned in all the four (highlighted in yellow). Furthermore, all the four DNA polymerases possess the typical DEDD(Y)-superfamily of PR exonucleases (highlighted in light blue).

Besides, a large number of consecutive Qs is found at the NTD in the human mitochondrial POLG1 (marked in red and highlighted in yellow) and discussed elsewhere. The catalytic metal-binding Ds are marked in red and are highlighted in dark green. Putative ZBMs (highlighted in orange) are found in the human mitochondrial POLG1 and Plant mitochondrial/chloroplast DNA pols IA and IB. Even though the PR exonuclease and polymerases active site amino acids are highly conserved.

BLASTp analysis of human POLG1 with other DNA polymerases showed only 36.92% identity to the DNA pol IB and the DNA pol IB did not show much similarity and the *E. coli* DNA pol I showed only 31.25%.

CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) 'Mix and Match' MSA of human mitochondrial POLG1, Plant mitochondrial/chloroplast DNA pols IA and IB, and *E. coli* DNA pol I.

sp P54098 DPOG1_HUMAN	SDGQRRR	Q00000	---Q00000	PQQPQVLSS	-----EGGQLRHNPLDIQMLSRG	82
sp P00582 DPO1_ECOLI	VSG---	VEADDVIGTLAREAEKAGRPVL	ISTGDKDMAQLVTPNITLINT-MTNTILGPE			163
sp F4I6M1 POLIA_ARATH	VGNQTEVAETHQVPGTVSAWREEAN	-----KLREERNQGIARN	-----			142
sp Q84ND9 POLIB_ARATH	-----QAGAVSAWREEVNN	-----KLRGRNREYANN	-----			122
		::			. . .	
sp P54098 DPOG1_HUMAN	-----EGEAVPVAIPEERALVF	---	DVEVCL	-----AEGT	CP	209
sp P00582 DPO1_ECOLI	ATVISYDNYVTILDE-ETLKAWIAK	---	LEKAPVFAF	DTE	ITDSLNDNISANLV---GLSF	373
sp F4I6M1 POLIA_ARATH	ENLGKIYDKVLIVDNVQAAKDTVAKLVNQFRNHVHSC	DTE	VSGIEVKEETPV	DHGELICF		316
sp Q84ND9 POLIB_ARATH	ANLKKIYNRVRVVDNVSSAKETVALLMNQYRNLVHAC	DTE	VSRI	DVKTETPV	DHGEMICF	294
		:	:	*	*.*	.

Table 1 shows the naturally occurring clinical variants in the proposed polymerase region (766-1239) of the *POLG1* gene. The disease mutations are highlighted in magenta (Fig. 1). Interestingly, some of the disease mutations are found clustered in the proposed catalytic core, viz. -R⁹⁴³EHAKIFNY⁹⁵¹GRIY⁹⁵⁵GA⁹⁵⁷- and in the metal-binding motifs, viz. -H¹¹³⁴DE- and -D¹¹⁸⁴ID- (highlighted in magenta).

Table 1 Clinical variants on the polymerase region (766-1239) of the human *POLG1* gene

Region	mt-Disease(s)*	Holoenzyme activity (p140+p55)	Reference
A ⁷⁶⁷ →D	MTDPS4A	-	PubMed:16621917
R ⁸⁰⁷ →C	SANDO	-	PubMed:16919951
R ⁸⁰⁷ →P	PEOB1(sporadic) -	-	PubMed:14635118
Y ⁸³¹ →C	PEOA1 & MTDPS4A	-	PubMed:15534189
Thumb:			
Wild-type	Nil	100%	[44]
G ⁸⁴⁸ →S	Alpers syndrome, Leigh syndrome, MELAS, PEO with ataxia-neuropathy, PEO.	0.03%	"
T ⁸⁵¹ →A	Alpers syndrome	0.92%	"
R ⁸⁵² →C	Alpers syndrome, Ataxia-neuropathy	0.32%	"
R ⁸⁵³ →Q	Myocerebrohepatopathy	0.09%	"
R ⁸⁵³ →W	PEOB1(ar1)	-	PubMed:16401742
N ⁸⁶⁴ →S	MTDPS4B	-	PubMed:12825077
Palm:			
Q ⁸⁷⁹ →H	Alpers syndrome with valproate-induced hepatic failure	28%	[44]
T ⁸⁸⁵ →S	Alpers syndrome with valproate-induced hepatic failure	58%	"
A ⁸⁸⁹ →T	PEOB1		PubMed:12975295
L ⁸⁹⁶ →R;	Ptosis, Ophthalmoplegia, Cataracts		
T ⁹¹⁴ →P	MTDPS4A		PubMed:16639411
G ⁹²³ →D	PEOA1	>50%	PubMed:1221079
H ⁹³² →Y	PEOB1, SANDO (sporadic)		[45]
NTP selection amino acid:			
R ⁹⁴³ →H	PEOA1 dominant	0.2%	[41]
Catalytic amino acid:			
K ⁹⁴⁷		-	
Polymerase catalytic core:			
Y ⁹⁵¹ →H	Ptosis, Ophthalmoplegia, Cataracts		
R ⁹⁵³ →C	PEOA1	-	PubMed:15351195
Template-binding pair (Y⁹⁵⁵G) region:			
Y ⁹⁵⁵ →C [@]	PEOA1 & Parkinsonism (most common, dominant) <0.1%		PubMed:11431686
Y ⁹⁵⁵ →H [#]	bilateral sensorineural hearing loss, cataract, myopathy, and liver failure	-	
A ⁹⁵⁷ →S ^{&}	PEOA1(dominant)		
A ⁹⁵⁷ →P	MTDPS4A		PubMed:15689359
Fingers:			
R ¹⁰⁴⁷ →Q	PEOB1 (sporadic)		PubMed:12707443
G ¹⁰⁵¹ →R	SANDO		PubMed:14745080
P ¹⁰⁷³ →L	MTDPS4A		[46]
G ¹⁰⁷⁶ →V	PEOB1		PubMed:12975295
R ¹⁰⁹⁶ →H	MTDPS4A		PubMed:16621917
S ¹¹⁰⁴ →C	PEOB1 (sporadic)		PubMed:12707443
A ¹¹⁰⁵ →T	PEOB1		PubMed:15351195
V ¹¹⁰⁶ →I	PEOB1		PubMed:15349879
H ¹¹¹⁰ →Y	MTDPS4A		PubMed:18828154
H ¹¹³⁴ →R	MTDPS4A		PubMed:18828154
E ¹¹³⁶ →K	MTDPS4A		PubMed:18828154
E ¹¹⁴³ →G	Breast cancer		[43]
R ¹¹⁴⁶ →C	PEOB1		PubMed:16401742
S ¹¹⁷⁶ →L	PEOA1		PubMed:12210792
D ¹¹⁸⁴ →N	PEOB1		PubMed:16401742
D ¹¹⁸⁶ →H	PEOA1		PubMed:18575922
K ¹¹⁹¹ →N	MTDPS4A		PubMed:16621917

Main source: From the Human mitochondrial genome database, www.mtddb.igp.uu.se and human mito gamma pol mutations.

*Most of them manifest in *trans* with other genetic mutations on the *POLG1* gene. **PEOA1**, Progressive external ophthalmoplegia with mitochondrial DNA deletions (Autosomal Dominant 1); **PEOB1**, autosomal recessive 1; (**AdPEO** mutations in *POLG1* are generally found in very conserved residues within the active site of the p140 DNA polymerase domain [41], while **ArPEO** mutations are spread throughout the gene). **MTDPS4A**, Mitochondrial DNA depletion syndrome, also known as Alpers syndrome, is an autosomal recessive disorder characterized by a clinical triad of psychomotor retardation, intractable epilepsy, and liver failure in infants and young children. **MTDPS4B**, Mitochondrial DNA depletion syndrome is an autosomal recessive, progressive, multisystem disorder which manifests as neurogastrointestinal encephalopathy (**MNGIE**). Patients with

clinical triad of Sensory Ataxic Neuropathy, Dysarthria, and Ophthalmoparesis (**SANDO**) is a variant of autosomal recessive **PEO (ArPEO)**.[@] and[#], both mutations affect mtDNA replication and display a dominant negative effect, with the Y⁹⁵⁵→H allele resulting in more severe polymerase dysfunction.

[&]In functional studies, the A⁹⁵⁷→P mutant showed the most striking deficiencies in the incorporation of a correct dNTP compared to the wild-type. The A⁹⁵⁷→P mutant had a 2-fold order of magnitude loss of fidelity compared to the wild-type, suggesting that a buildup of mitochondrial mutations may contribute to death in infancy in those with this mutation [47].

Figure 4 shows the MSA of the NEPs from human and various animal sources (Only the regions required for the discussions are shown here). The human sequence is used as the reference and highlighted in yellow. The N-terminal region of ~470 amino acids showed many gaps and mismatches in the alignment (data not shown), after that, conservations are observed and a clear demarcation (marked with an arrow) of the PR exonuclease domain is seen (highlighted in red). The first triad, -DTE- type of the DEDD-superfamily of the PR exonucleases is not completely conserved among the NEPs from humans and various animal sources (the humans and chimpanzees use, unusually an A in the first triad, as -DAE- and in many others the third amino acid E is replaced by a Q). However, strikingly the other three active site amino acids are completely conserved (highlighted in light blue) with an invariant H as the proton acceptor in the PR exonuclease domain (Table 2).

Again, after ~830 amino acids, a second demarcation in the sequences is seen (marked by an arrow) and it contains the polymerase active site amino acids (highlighted in yellow). The polymerase region is highly conserved among them, but the catalytic core region is completely conserved in all NEPs from human and animal sources. It contains the template-binding -YG- pair, the catalytic amino acid K, and the nucleotide discriminating amino acid R at -4 from the catalytic K. The POLG1 active site, -TR⁴KVVK⁹⁹¹Q¹TVMTVVY⁸GV- is almost identical to the other NEPs of plant chloroplasts and mitochondria, (-DR⁴KLVK⁷⁵²Q¹TVMTSVY⁸GV-), and is found to be very similar to the confirmed active site of *E. coli* DNA pol I, -QR⁴RSK⁷⁵⁸A¹INFG¹LY⁸GM- [36] and in close agreement to the active sites of the other DNA/RNA polymerases already reported [37] (Table 3). The human and animal sequences showed an additional -YG- pair (highlighted in light yellow) downstream from the proposed template-binding YG pair. The proposed catalytic metal-binding Ds in -HQD⁹²²- and -HD¹¹⁵¹C- motifs are completely conserved (highlighted in dark green). SDM data have shown that the substitutions of the Ds in -AFD⁵³⁷G- and -HD⁸¹²S motifs to D⁵³⁷→N and D⁸¹²→N in T7 RNAP resulted in the complete loss of activity [48, 49]. Almost all the NEPs (except the sequence from lion) invariably end in a hexapeptide -STYFFS- and its significance is not clear now. Unlike the self-sustained T7 RNAP, NEP needs transcription factors for promoter recognition, like TFAM and TFB2M, and also a transcription elongation factor, TEFM. (TFAM binds to the mitochondrial promoter's sequence and creates a stable protein-DNA complex. TFAM and TFB2M work synergistically to support mitochondrial transcription initiation) [50].

An unusual capping structure is found in the mt-mRNAs. In contrast to an m⁷G cap usually found at the 5' n-mRNAs, (which is added to the nascent mRNAs by a capping complex that is associated with eukaryotic RNA polymerase II), the SSU mitochondrial RNA polymerase (mt-RNAP) caps its mRNAs with NAD⁺ and NADH. An NAD⁺ cap is added by the mt-RNAP itself during transcription initiation, which serves as a non-canonical initiating nucleotide [51]. However, like the n-mRNAs, the human mt-mRNAs are stabilized by polyadenylation which is regulated by the mitochondria-specific poly-(A) polymerase and polynucleotide phosphorylase [52]. Interestingly, inhibitors of mtDNA transcription, targeting the mt-RNAP, reduce mitochondrial metabolism and ATP levels. The mt-RNAP inhibitors, viz. IMT1 and IMT1B have been shown to reduce cancer cell growth and viability *in vitro* and induce strong antitumor responses [53].

CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) MSA of mitochondrial NEPs from human and various animal sources

	NTD	PR Exo	
tr HOVY05 HOVY05_CAVPO	LYP	FLCVLPEEELVQILLQVLFSLPAQGEFVHTAHRLALQTFQRHILRQSCRGHQLQAL	493
tr AOA2J8RA74 AOA2J8RA74_PONAB	LYP	FLCCLLDEREVVRMLLQVLQALPAQGESFTTLARELSARTFSRHVVQRQRSLSGQVQAL	526
sp O00411 RPOM_HUMAN	LYP	FLCCLLDEREVVRMLLQVLQALPAQGESFTTLARELSARTFSRHVVQRQRVSGQVQAL	526
tr H2QES6 H2QES6_PANTR	LYP	FLCCLLDEREVVRMLLQVLQALPAQGESFTTLARELSARTFSRHVVQRQRVSGQVQAL	526
tr F7GCL4 F7GCL4_CALJA	MFP	FLCCLLGEQEMVQMLLQALQALPAQGESFMGLARDLGARTFSRHEVQRQFSGQVEAL	525
tr AOA2K6TCW0_SAIBB	MFP	FLCCLLDEQEMVGMMLLQTLQALPTQGESFMGLARDLGARTFARHEVQRQFSGQVEAL	524
tr AOA1U7QPL6 AOA1U7QPL6_MESAU	LYP	FLCCLLEEEFVSMMLQALRLLPAQGEPLHLAHLADLGLRVNLRLHVKKKQETNHVQKL	490
tr D3ZYB6 D3ZYB6_RAT	LYP	FLCCLLEGEFVSIIMQALQVLPAQGEPLFQLAQNGLQVFNRLHVKQKQVTNHVQKL	496
sp Q8BKF1 RPOM_MOUSE	LYP	FLCCLLEGEFVSIIMQVVKVLPAAQGEPLIQLAHLNGLRVNLRLHVKQKQVTNHVQKL	498
tr G3SPD8 G3SPD8_LOXAF	LYP	HLCLLSERQMAQMLLQVLQVLPQGESLIHLAHELGMRTFNRYVVRQKREHQVQAL	500
tr I3M2A6 I3M2A6_ICTR	LFP	FLCCLLSERELVVRMLLQALYALPAQGESLVVVAKDLGLRFTFNRRHMVQKRLNNQVQAL	509
tr AOA8C8WQE5 AOA8C8WQE5_PANLE	LFP	FLCCLLSERELVVRMLLQALYALPAQGESLVVVAKDLGLRFTFNRRHMVQKRLNNQVQAL	430
tr AOA8I3NVE4 AOA8I3NVE4_CANLF	LFP	FLCCLLSERELVVRMLLQALYALPAQGESLVVVAKDLGLRFTFNRRHMVQKRLNNQVQAL	513
tr AOA452S012 AOA452S012_URSAM	LFP	FLCCLLSERELVVRMLLQALYALPAQGESLVVVAKDLGLRFTFNRRHMVQKRLNNQVQAL	519
tr G1L7Q8 G1L7Q8_AILME	LFP	FLCCLLSERELVVRMLLQALYALPAQGESLVVVAKDLGLRFTFNRRHMVQKRLNNQVQAL	578
tr AOA671FMH5 AOA671FMH5_RHIFE	LFP	FLCCLLSERELVVRMLLQALYALPAQGESLVVVAKDLGLRFTFNRRHMVQKRLNNQVQAL	517
tr AOA4X1VUE2 AOA4X1VUE2_PIG	LFP	FLCCLLSERELVVRMLLQALYALPAQGESLVVVAKDLGLRFTFNRRHMVQKRLNNQVQAL	508
tr AOA5F5PY63 AOA5F5PY63_HORSE	LFP	FLCCLLSERELVVRMLLQALYALPAQGESLVVVAKDLGLRFTFNRRHMVQKRLNNQVQAL	519
tr AOA452EG30 AOA452EG30_CAPHI	LFP	FLCCLLSERELVVRMLLQALYALPAQGESLVVVAKDLGLRFTFNRRHMVQKRLNNQVQAL	505
tr AOA5N3WLT3 AOA5N3WLT3_MUNMU	LFP	FLCCLLSERELVVRMLLQALYALPAQGESLVVVAKDLGLRFTFNRRHMVQKRLNNQVQAL	510
tr AOA5N4CMK3 AOA5N4CMK3_CAMDR	LFP	FLCCLLSERELVVRMLLQALYALPAQGESLVVVAKDLGLRFTFNRRHMVQKRLNNQVQAL	521
tr AOA2Y9MQK8 AOA2Y9MQK8_DELLE	LFP	FLCCLLSERELVVRMLLQALYALPAQGESLVVVAKDLGLRFTFNRRHMVQKRLNNQVQAL	518
tr AOA340XK43 AOA340XK43_LIPVE	LFP	FLCCLLSERELVVRMLLQALYALPAQGESLVVVAKDLGLRFTFNRRHMVQKRLNNQVQAL	518

tr H0VY05 H0VY05_CAVPO	EQRKYAKYLGLLAS	DTC	-----	509
tr AOA2J8RA74 AOA2J8RA74_PONAB	QNHYRKYLCLLAC	DTE	-----	542
sp O00411 RPOM_HUMAN	QNHYRKYLCLLAS	DAE	-----	542
tr H2QES6 H2QES6_PANTR	QNHYRKYLCLLAS	DAE	-----	542
tr F7GCL4 F7GCL4_CALJA	KRHYRQYLHLLAA	DTE	-----	541
tr AOA2K6TCW0_SAIBB	KRQYRQYLHLLAS	DTE	-----	540
tr AOA1U7QPL6 AOA1U7QPL6_MESAU	GQHSYQYLRLLAS	DTC	-----	506
tr D3ZYB6 D3ZYB6_RAT	GQQYSQYLRLLAS	DTC	-----	512
sp Q8BKF1 RPOM_MOUSE	GQRYSQYLQLLAS	DTC	-----	514
tr G3SPD8 G3SPD8_LOXAF	QRRYSEYLRLAC	DTC	-----	516
tr I3M2A6 I3M2A6 ICTTR	EQRYAQYLHLLAC	DTC	-----	525
tr AOA8C8WQE5 AOA8C8WQE5_PANLE	-----LL-----	---	-----GGRAGCGPGSSPWVAHRQERRGGPRPGGGGG	463
tr AOA8I3NVE4 AOA8I3NVE4_CANLF	QQRYYRYLHLLAS	DTC	VRPGTRASLLPSLPGAAGSDGPRPLAPG----WLSPCPRGWPG	569
tr AOA452S012 AOA452S012_URSAM	RQRYYRYLQLLAS	DTC	-----	535
tr G1L7Q8 G1L7Q8_AILME	QRRYYRYLHLLAS	DTC	-----	594
tr AOA671FMH5 AOA671FMH5_RHIFE	ERRYFEYLRLLAS	DSF	-----	533
tr AOA4X1VUE2 AOA4X1VUE2_PIG	EKQYSKYLHLLAS	DTC	-----	524
tr AOA5F5PY63 AOA5F5PY63_HORSE	EKRYSQYLHLLAS	DAC	-----	535
tr AOA452EG30 AOA452EG30_CAPHI	EQRYSKYLHLLAS	DTC	-----	521
tr AOA5N3WLT3 AOA5N3WLT3_MUNMU	EQRYSKYLHLLAS	DTC	-----	526
tr AOA5N4CMK3 AOA5N4CMK3_CAMDR	EQHYIKYLHLLAS	DTC	-----	537
tr AOA2Y9MQK8 AOA2Y9MQK8_DELLE	EQRYSKYLHLLAS	DTC	-----	534
tr AOA340XK43 AOA340XK43_LIPVE	EQRYSKYLHLLAS	DTC	-----	534

tr H0VY05 H0VY05_CAVPO	PHLKAQLRQEVARCLKVAREMHGLRQEALYRLSLAQHLRD-RV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	756
tr AOA2J8RA74 AOA2J8RA74_PONAB	PARKAEVRRGLAHCQKVAREMHSLRAEALYRLSLAQHLRD-RV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	810
sp O00411 RPOM_HUMAN	PARKAELRRELAHCQKVAREMHSLRAEALYRLSLAQHLRD-RV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	810
tr H2QES6 H2QES6_PANTR	PARKAELRREVVHCQKVAREMHSLRAEALYRLSLAQHLRD-RV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	810
tr F7GCL4 F7GCL4_CALJA	LVDKAE LRRELARSLKESREMHS LRADALYRLSLADHLRN-CV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	809
tr AOA2K6TCW0_SAIBB	LADKAE LRRELARCLKEAREMHS LRTEALYRLSLAQHLRN-RV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	808
tr AOA1U7QPL6 AOA1U7QPL6_MESAU	PVHKAE LRKELSRCLKAAREMHS LRIEALYRLSLAQYLRN-RV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	774
tr D3ZYB6 D3ZYB6_RAT	PVHKSELRKLARCLKAAREMHS LRSEALYRLSLAQHLRD-RV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	779
sp Q8BKF1 RPOM_MOUSE	PVHKSELRKLARCLKVAREMHS LRSEALYRLSLAQHLRH-RV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	781
tr G3SPD8 G3SPD8_LOXAF	PARLAELRREVARCLKAAREMHS LRADALYRLSLAQHLRHGAF	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	791
tr I3M2A6 I3M2A6 ICTTR	PAHKAE LRRELAGCLKVAREMHS LRVDALYRLSLAQHLRH-RV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	793
tr AOA8C8WQE5 AOA8C8WQE5_PANLE	PAQKAE LRRELARCLKVAREMHS LRSDALYRLSLAQHLRH-CV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	749
tr AOA8I3NVE4 AOA8I3NVE4_CANLF	PAQKAE VRRELARCLKVAREMHS LRSDALYRLSLAQHLRH-RV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	853
tr AOA452S012 AOA452S012_URSAM	SAQKAE VRREVARCLKVAREMHS LRSDALYRLSLAQHLRD-RV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	803
tr G1L7Q8 G1L7Q8_AILME	SAQKAE VRREVARCLKVAREMHS LRSDALYRLSLAQHLRD-RV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	862
tr AOA671FMH5 AOA671FMH5_RHIFE	PEHKAELRRELARCLKVAREMHS LRTEALYRLSLAQHLRH-RV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	801
tr AOA4X1VUE2 AOA4X1VUE2_PIG	PTQKAE LRRELARLRKMAEMHS LRTEALYRLSMAQHLRG-RV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	798
tr AOA5F5PY63 AOA5F5PY63_HORSE	PARKAELRRELARCLKVAREMHS LRADALYRLSLAQHLRH-RV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	803
tr AOA452EG30 AOA452EG30_CAPHI	PADKAE MRRELARLRKVAREMHS LRADALYRLSLAQHLRN-HV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	786
tr AOA5N3WLT3 AOA5N3WLT3_MUNMU	PADKAE MRRELARLRKVAREMHS LRADALYRLSLAQHLRN-HV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	800
tr AOA5N4CMK3 AOA5N4CMK3_CAMDR	PADKAE MRRELARLRKVAREMHS LRADALYRLSLAQHLRH-RV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	811
tr AOA2Y9MQK8 AOA2Y9MQK8_DELLE	PAEKAEMRRELARLRKVAREMHS LRADALYRLSLAQHLRH-RV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	808
tr AOA340XK43 AOA340XK43_LIPVE	PAEKAEMRRELARLRKVAREMHS LRADALYRLSLAQHLRH-RV	FWLPHNMD	FRGRTYPCP	808

tr H0VY05 H0VY05_CAVPO	PHFNHLGSDVARALLEFAQGRP	PR Exo ↑	Pol	LGPRGIDWLKIHVLNLTGLKREPLRHARLSFADAMDD	816
tr AOA2J8RA74 AOA2J8RA74_PONAB	PHFNHLGSDVARALLEFAQGRP			LGPRGIDWLKIHVLNLTGLKREPLRKRLLAFAEVMD	870
sp O00411 RPOM_HUMAN	PHFNHLGSDVARALLEFAQGRP			LGPHGLDWLKIHLVNLTLGLKREPLRKRLLAFAEVMD	870
tr H2QES6 H2QES6_PANTR	PHFNHLGSDVARALLEFAQGRP			LGPHGLDWLKIHLVNLTLGLKREPLRKRLLAFAEVMD	870
tr F7GCL4 F7GCL4_CALJA	PHFNHLGNDLARALLEFAQGRP			LGPHGLDWLKIHVNLTLGLKREPLQVRHAFAEVMD	869
tr AOA2K6TCW0_SAIBB	PHFNHLGNDLARALLEFAQGRP			LGPHGLDWLKIHVNLTLGLKREPLQARRAFAEVMD	868
tr AOA1U7QPL6 AOA1U7QPL6_MESAU	PHFNHLGSDVARALLEFAQGRP			LGPRGIDWLKIHVLNLTGLKRDLSLRMLAFADAVMEE	834
tr D3ZYB6 D3ZYB6_RAT	PHFNHLGSDLARALLEFAEGRP			LGPRGIDWLKIHVLNLTGLKRDLSLRMLAFADAVMGE	839
sp Q8BKF1 RPOM_MOUSE	PHFNHLGSDLARALLEFAEGRP			LGPRGIDWLKIHVLNLTGLKRDLSLRMLAFADAVMEE	841
tr G3SPD8 G3SPD8_LOXAF	PHFNHLGSDLARALLEFAQGRP			LGPHGLDWLKIHLVNLTLGLKRESLQARLAFADQVLE	851
tr I3M2A6 I3M2A6 ICTTR	PHFNHLGSDLARALLEFAEGRP			LGPHGLTWLKIHLVNLTLGLKRDLSLQARLAFADQMDH	853
tr AOA8C8WQE5 AOA8C8WQE5_PANLE	PHFNHLGSDLARALLEFAQGRP			LGPRGIDWLKIHVLNLTGLKREPLQARLVFADEVMD	809
tr AOA8I3NVE4 AOA8I3NVE4_CANLF	PHFNHLGSDLARALLEFAQGRP			LGPHGLDWLKIHLVNLTLGLKREPLQARLVFADEVMD	913
tr AOA452S012 AOA452S012_URSAM	PHFNHLGSDLARALLEFAQGRP			LGPRGIDWLKIHVLNLTGLKREPLRRLVFADEVMD	863
tr G1L7Q8 G1L7Q8_AILME	PHFNHLGSDLARALLEFAQGRP			LGPHGLDWLKIHLVNLTLGLKREPLRRLVFADEVMD	922
tr AOA671FMH5 AOA671FMH5_RHIFE	PHFNHLGSDLARALLEFAQGRP			LGPHGLDWLKIHLVNLTLGLKRESLQARLAFADAVMD	861
tr AOA4X1VUE2 AOA4X1VUE2_PIG	PHFNHLGSDLARALLEFAQGRP			LGPGIENWLKIHLVNLTLGLKHESLQARRDLADELMD	858
tr AOA5F5PY63 AOA5F5PY63_HORSE	PHFNHLGSDLARALLEFAQGRP			LGPHGLDWLKIHLVNLTLGLKRESLQARRDLAFADAVMD	863
tr AOA452EG30 AOA452EG30_CAPHI	PHFNHLGSDLARALLEFAQGRP			LGPHGLDWLKIHLVNLTLGLKRESLQARRDYADAVMD	846
tr AOA5N3WLT3 AOA5N3WLT3_MUNMU	PHFNHLGSDLARALLEFAQGRP			LGPNGLDWLKIHLVNLTLGLKRESLQARRDYADAVMD	860
tr AOA5N4CMK3 AOA5N4CMK3_CAMDR	PHFNHLGSDLARALLEFAQGRP			LGPHGLDWLKIHLVNLTLGLKRESLQARRDFADQVLE	871
tr AOA2Y9MQK8 AOA2Y9MQK8_DELLE	PHFNHLGSDLARALLEFAQGRP			LGPHGLNWLKIHLVNLTLGLKRESLQARRDYADELMD	868
tr AOA340XK43 AOA340XK43_LIPVE	PHFNHLGSDLARALLEFAQGRP			LGPHGLNWLKIHLVNLTLGLKRESLQARRDYADQVLE	868

tr H0VY05 H0VY05_CAVPO	ILDSAERPM GRKWWMEADDEPWQTLACCMEVA RAVQSE DPAAYVSHLPV HODGSCNGLQH	876
tr A0A2J8RA74 A0A2J8RA74_PONAB	ILDSADQPL GRKWWMEAEPEPWQTLACCMEVA KAVRAS DPAAYVSHLPV HODGSCNGLQH	930
sp O00411 RPOM_HUMAN	ILDSADQPL GRKWWMEAEPEPWQTLACCMEVA NAVRA DPAAYVSHLPV HODGSCNGLQH	930
tr H2QES6 H2QES6_PANTR	ILDSADQPL GRKWWMEAEPEPWQTLACCMEVA NAVRA DPAAYVSHLPV HODGSCNGLQH	930
tr F7GCL4 F7GCL4_CALJA	ILDSADNPM GRKWWMGSEEPWQTLACCMEIA KAVRTS DPAAYVSHLPV HODGSCNGLQH	929
tr A0A2K6TCW0_SAIBB	ILDSADHPM GRKWWMDSEEPWQTLACCMEIA KAVRTS DPAAYVSHLPV HODGSCNGLQH	928
tr A0A1U7QPL6 A0A1U7QPL6_MESAU	ILDSADNPM GRKWWMDAEPWQTLACCMEVA QAVRSE DPAAYVSHLPV HODGSCNGLQH	894
tr D3ZYB6 D3ZYB6_RAT	ILDSADNPM GQKWWMKADEPWQTLACCMEVA QAVRSE DPAAYVSHLPV HODGSCNGLQH	899
sp Q8BKF1 RPOM_MOUSE	ILDSADNPM GRKWWMEADDEPWQTLACCMEVA HAVRSE DPAAYVSHLPV HODGSCNGLQH	901
tr G3SPD8 G3SPD8_LOXAF	VLDSADRPM GRKWWMEADDEPWQTLACCMEIA RALRSE DPTSFVSHFPV HODGSCNGLQH	911
tr I3M2A6 I3M2A6 ICTTR	ILDSADQPM GRKWWMESEEPWQTLACCMEVA QAVRAE DPAAYVSHLPV HODGSCNGLQH	913
tr A0A8C8WQE5 A0A8C8WQE5_PANLE	VLDSADRPM GRKWWMEVEEPWQALACCMEIA RAVRAE DPAAYVSHFPV HODGSCNGLQH	869
tr A0A8I3NVE4 A0A8I3NVE4_CANLF	ILDSADRPM GRKWWMEVEDEPWQALACCMEIA RAVRAE DPTAFVSHFPV HODGSCNGLQH	973
tr A0A452S012 A0A452S012_URSAM	ILDSADRPM GRKWWMEVEDEPWQALACCMEIA RAVRAE DPTAYVSHFPV HODGSCNGLQH	923
tr G1L7Q8 G1L7Q8_AILME	ILDSADRPM GRKWWMEADDEPWQALACCMEIA RAVRTA DPTAYVSHFPV HODGSCNGLQH	982
tr A0A671FMH5 A0A671FMH5_RHIFE	ILDSADRPM GRKWWMEADDEPWQALACCMEIA QAVRAG DPATHVSHFPV HODGSCNGLQH	921
tr A0A4X1VUE2 A0A4X1VUE2_PIG	ILDSADRPM GRKWWMEADDEPWQTLACCMEIA RAVRAE DPTAYVSHFPV HODGSCNGLQH	918
tr A0A5F5PY63 A0A5F5PY63_HORSE	ILDSADRPM GRKWWMEADDEPWQALACCMEIA RASRSE DPAAYVSHFPV HODGSCNGLQH	923
tr A0A452EG30 A0A452EG30_CAPHI	ILDSAERPM GRKWWMEADDEPWQTLACCMEIA QVHSE DPTTYISHFPV HODGSCNGLQH	906
tr A0A5N3WLT3 A0A5N3WLT3_MUNMU	ILDSAERPM GRKWWMEADDEPWQALACCMEIA QVHSE DPTTYISHFPV HODGSCNGLQH	920
tr A0A5N4CMK3 A0A5N4CMK3_CAMDR	ILDSADQPM GRKWWMEADDEPWQALACCMEIA RAVRAE DPAAYVSHFPV HODGSCNGLQH	931
tr A0A2Y9MQK8 A0A2Y9MQK8_DELLE	ILDSADRPM GRKWWMEADDEPWQALACCMEVA RAVRAE DPTAYVSHFPV HODGSCNGLQH	928
tr A0A340XK43 A0A340XK43_LIPVE	ILDSADRPM GRKWWMEADDEPWQALACCMEVA RAVRAE DPTAYVSHFPV HODGSCNGLQH	928
	:****:.*: :*:*** :****:*****:*. . . : **:.:.*:*****:***	

tr H0VY05 H0VY05_CAVPO	YALGRDSVGAASVNLASSDVPQDVYSGVAAQVEVFRRQDAQKGVKVAQVLEGFITR KVV	936
tr A0A2J8RA74 A0A2J8RA74_PONAB	YALGRDSVGAASVNLLEPSDVPQDVYSGVAAQVEVFRRQDAQKGVKVAQVLEGFITR KVV	990
sp O00411 RPOM_HUMAN	YALGRDSVGAASVNLLEPSDVPQDVYSGVAAQVEVFRRQDAQKGVKVAQVLEGFITR KVV	990
tr H2QES6 H2QES6_PANTR	YALGRDSVGAASVNLLEPSDVPQDVYSGVAAQVEVFRRQDAQKGVKVAQVLEGFITR KVV	990
tr F7GCL4 F7GCL4_CALJA	YALGRDSVGAASVNLLEPSDVPQDVYSDVAAQVEVFRRQDARRGSRVAQVLEGFVTR KVV	989
tr A0A2K6TCW0_SAIBB	YALGRDSVGAASVNLLEPAEVPQDVYSDVAAQVEVFRRQDARRGSRVAQVLEGFVTR KVV	988
tr A0A1U7QPL6 A0A1U7QPL6_MESAU	YALGRDSAGAASVNLMPDLPQDVYREVAAQVEVFRQDADQGLRQADQVLEGFITR KVV	954
tr D3ZYB6 D3ZYB6_RAT	YALGRDSVGAASVNLTPSDLPQDVYREVATQVEELRQDQDAKEGLQVAQVLEGFVTR KVV	959
sp Q8BKF1 RPOM_MOUSE	YALGRDSVGAASVNLTPSDLPQDVYREVATQVEELRQDQDAKEGLRVAQVLEGFISR KVV	961
tr G3SPD8 G3SPD8_LOXAF	YALGRDSVGAASVNLTPSDLPQDVYREVAAQVEVFRQDAEQGVRVAQVLEGFISR KVV	971
tr I3M2A6 I3M2A6 ICTTR	YALGRDSVGAASVNLLEPSDLPQDVYSGVAAQVEVFRRQDAARGVRRVAQVLEGFISR KVV	973
tr A0A8C8WQE5 A0A8C8WQE5_PANLE	YALGRDSIGAASVNLLEPSDVPQDVYSGVAAQVEVFRRQDAKRGVRRVAQVLEGFISR KVV	929
tr A0A8I3NVE4 A0A8I3NVE4_CANLF	YALGRDSIGAASVNLLEPSDVPQDVYSGVAAQVEVFRRQDAQKGVRRVAQVLEGFISR KVV	1033
tr A0A452S012 A0A452S012_URSAM	YALGRDSVGAASVNLLEPSDLPQDVYSGVAAQVEVFRRQDAERGVRVAQVLEGFISR KVV	983
tr G1L7Q8 G1L7Q8_AILME	YALGRDSVGAASVNLLEPSDLPQDVYSGVAAQVEVFRRQDAERGVRVAQVLEGFISR KVV	1042
tr A0A671FMH5 A0A671FMH5_RHIFE	YALGRDSVGAASVNLVPSDLPQDVYSGVATQVEVFRRQDAERGVRVAQVLEGFISR KVV	981
tr A0A4X1VUE2 A0A4X1VUE2_PIG	YALGRDSAGAASVNLMPDLPQDVYREVAAQVEVFRQDAEQGMRVAQVLEGFISR KVV	978
tr A0A5F5PY63 A0A5F5PY63_HORSE	YALGRDSVGAASVNLVPSDLPQDVYSGVAAQVEVFRRQDAEQGVRVAQVLEGFISR KVV	983
tr A0A452EG30 A0A452EG30_CAPHI	YALGRDSTGATSVNLSPDLPQDVYSEVAAQVEVFRQDAKQGVRRVAQVLEGFISR KVV	966
tr A0A5N3WLT3 A0A5N3WLT3_MUNMU	YALGRDSTGAASVNLSPDLPQDVYSEVAAQVEVFRQDAKQGVRRVAQVLEGFISR KVV	980
tr A0A5N4CMK3 A0A5N4CMK3_CAMDR	YALGRDSVGAASVNLLEPSDLPQDVYSGVAAQVEVFRRQDAEQGVRVAQVLEGFISR KVV	991
tr A0A2Y9MQK8 A0A2Y9MQK8_DELLE	YALGRDSVGAASVNLLEPSDLPQDVYSEVAAQVEVFRQDAEQGVRVAQVLEGFISR KVV	988
tr A0A340XK43 A0A340XK43_LIPVE	YALGRDSVGAASVNLLEPSDLPQDVYSEVAAQVEVFRQDAEQGVRVAQVLEGFISR KVV	988
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tr H0VY05 H0VY05_CAVPO	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI PTFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	996
tr A0A2J8RA74 A0A2J8RA74_PONAB	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI SDFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	1050
sp O00411 RPOM_HUMAN	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI SDFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	1050
tr H2QES6 H2QES6_PANTR	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI SDFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	1050
tr F7GCL4 F7GCL4_CALJA	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI SDFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	1049
tr A0A2K6TCW0_SAIBB	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI SDFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	1048
tr A0A1U7QPL6 A0A1U7QPL6_MESAU	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI SNFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	1014
tr D3ZYB6 D3ZYB6_RAT	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI SDFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	1019
sp Q8BKF1 RPOM_MOUSE	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI SDFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	1021
tr G3SPD8 G3SPD8_LOXAF	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI PDPFQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	1031
tr I3M2A6 I3M2A6 ICTTR	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI SDFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	1033
tr A0A8C8WQE5 A0A8C8WQE5_PANLE	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI SDFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	989
tr A0A8I3NVE4 A0A8I3NVE4_CANLF	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI SNFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	1093
tr A0A452S012 A0A452S012_URSAM	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI SNFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	1043
tr G1L7Q8 G1L7Q8_AILME	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI SNFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	1102
tr A0A671FMH5 A0A671FMH5_RHIFE	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI SDFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	1041
tr A0A4X1VUE2 A0A4X1VUE2_PIG	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI QDFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	1038
tr A0A5F5PY63 A0A5F5PY63_HORSE	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI SDFPQ-----	1015
tr A0A452EG30 A0A452EG30_CAPHI	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI EDFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	1026
tr A0A5N3WLT3 A0A5N3WLT3_MUNMU	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI EDFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	1040
tr A0A5N4CMK3 A0A5N4CMK3_CAMDR	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI HDFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	1051
tr A0A2Y9MQK8 A0A2Y9MQK8_DELLE	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI HDFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	1048
tr A0A340XK43 A0A340XK43_LIPVE	KQFVMTVY GVT YGGRLQIEKRLREI HDFPQEFVWEASHYLVRQVFKSLQEMFSGTRAI	1048
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Figure 5 shows the ‘Mix and Match’ MSA of all the three NEPs from the human mitochondria and from the mitochondria and chloroplasts from plants (*A. Thaliana*) (Only the regions required for the discussions are shown here). Even though the DEDD-superfamily of PR exonuclease active site amino acids are completely conserved in all the three NEPs from human and plant, the first triad does not align. However, all the other three active site amino acids align and are completely conserved in all three NEPs (highlighted in light blue) (Fig. 5). The RNA polymerase active site and metal-binding site amino acids are completely conserved in all three NEPs (highlighted in yellow and dark green, respectively). Putative ZBMs are highlighted in orange. The NEPs from plant mitochondria and chloroplasts end in -YFFN- whereas the human and animal NEP ends in -YFFS- (Figs. 4, 5).

CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) ‘Mix and Match’ MSA of all the three NEPs from both human and plant

Figure 5 ‘Mix and Match’ MSA of all the three NEPs from both human and plant

Table 2 DEDD-superfamily exonuclease active site amino acids and their distance conservations.

DEDD-Superfamily of PR Exonucleases (DEED*(H*/Y*))	
Phage DNA Polymerases	
T4 DNA pol (<i>E. coli</i> Phage)	D ¹¹⁴ ----- F ²¹⁹ ----- S ³²⁰ N →3 aa← D ³²⁴ VE - [54]
T7 DNA pol (<i>E. coli</i> Phage)	D ¹¹⁴ ----- F ²³⁵ ----- D ¹⁷⁰ N →3 aa← D ¹⁷⁴ VV -
Prokaryotic DNA Polymerases and RNases	
DNA pol I (<i>E. coli</i>)	D ³⁵⁵ T ³⁵⁷ ----- Y ⁴²⁴ ----- R ⁴⁹⁷ A →3 aa← D ⁵⁰¹ AD -
DNA pol II (<i>E. coli</i>)	D ¹⁵⁶ E ¹⁵⁸ ----- F ²²⁹ ----- T ³³¹ N →3 aa← D ³³⁵ CE -
RNase D (<i>E. coli</i>)	D ²⁸ T ³⁰ ----- D ¹⁰² ----- E ¹⁵¹ A →3 aa← D ¹⁵⁵ VW -
RNase T (<i>E. coli</i>)	D ²³ V ²⁵ ----- F ¹²⁵ ----- A ¹⁸¹ S →4 aa← D ¹⁸⁶ TE -
Prokaryotic DNA Replicases (DNA pol III-ε-subunits)	
<i>E. coli</i>	D ¹² T ----- F ¹⁰² ----- L ¹⁶² G →4 aa← D ¹⁶⁷ AQ -
<i>Citrobacter amalonaticus</i>	D ¹⁵ T E ----- F ¹⁰⁵ ----- L ¹⁶⁵ G →4 aa← D ¹⁷⁰ AQ -
<i>Shigella dysenteriae</i>	D ¹² T E ----- F ¹⁰² ----- L ¹⁶² G →4 aa← D ¹⁶⁷ AQ -
<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>	D ¹² T E ----- F ¹⁰² ----- L ¹⁶² G →4 aa← D ¹⁶⁷ AQ -
Eukaryotic DNA Replicases	
DNA pol ε cat. subunit (<i>Sc</i>)	D ²⁹⁰ I ----- F ³⁸³ ----- E ⁴⁷³ S →3 aa← D ⁴⁷⁷ AV - [55, 56]
DNA pol δ cat. subunit (<i>Hs</i>)	D ³¹⁶ E ----- F ⁴⁰² ----- V ⁵¹¹ C →3 aa← D ⁵¹⁵ AY - [57]
Plant DNA Polymerases IA (Plant Chloroplasts)[#]	
<i>Arabidopsis Thaliana</i>	D ²⁹⁴ T E ----- F ³⁹⁸ S ----- S ⁴⁷⁰ S →3 aa← D ⁴⁷⁴ AI -
<i>Chlorella desiccata</i>	D ²⁹⁴ T E ----- F ³⁹⁴ R ----- S ⁴⁹⁵ S →3 aa← D ⁴⁹⁹ AK -
<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i>	D ⁴⁴⁷ T E ----- F ⁵²¹ S ----- F ⁶³⁴ S →3 aa← D ⁶³⁸ SI -
<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	D ²⁸⁴ T E ----- F ³⁸⁸ S ----- S ⁴⁶⁰ S →3 aa← D ⁴⁶⁴ AI -
Plant DNA Polymerases IB (Plant Chloroplasts)[#]	
<i>Arabidopsis Thaliana</i>	D ²⁷² T E ----- F ³⁴⁶ N ----- S ⁴⁴⁸ S →3 aa← D ⁴⁵² SI -
<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	D ³⁹⁰ T E ----- F ⁴⁰⁸ N ----- C ⁵⁷² S →3 aa← D ⁵⁷⁶ SI -
<i>Sesamum indicum</i>	D ³⁴⁰ T E ----- F ⁴⁴⁶ N ----- S ⁵⁰³ S →3 aa← D ⁵⁰⁶ SI -
<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	D ²⁹⁸ T E ----- F ³⁹² N ----- S ⁴³⁴ S →3 aa← D ⁴³⁸ SI -
<i>E. coli</i> DNA pol I Exo [#]	D ⁹³⁶ T E ----- Y ⁹³⁶ ----- R ⁴⁹⁷ A →3 aa← D ⁵⁰¹ AD -
Nuclear-Encoded RNA Polymerases (NEPs) from Plant Chloroplasts[#]	
<i>Arabidopsis Thaliana</i>	D ⁵⁴⁸ VE ----- L ⁵⁷² F ----- N ⁵⁸⁶ L →3 aa← D ⁵⁹⁰ LC -
<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>	D ⁵⁷⁵ VE ----- V ⁵⁹³ F ----- N ⁶¹³ L →3 aa← D ⁶¹⁷ LC -
<i>Oryza rufipogon</i>	D ⁵³⁸ VE ----- L ⁵⁶² F ----- N ⁵⁷⁶ L →3 aa← D ⁵⁸⁰ LC -
<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i>	D ⁵⁸⁶ VE ----- L ⁶¹⁰ F ----- N ³⁹⁵ L →3 aa← D ⁵²⁸ LC -
Nuclear-Encoded RNA Polymerases (NEPs) from Plant Mitochondria[#]	
<i>Arabidopsis Thaliana</i>	D ¹⁰⁵ VE ----- V ⁶⁰⁵ F ----- N ⁶⁰³ L →3 aa← D ⁵⁷⁵ LC -
<i>Brassica napus</i>	D ¹⁹⁶ VE ----- L ⁷⁸⁷ F ----- N ⁸⁰⁸ L →3 aa← D ⁷⁹⁷ LC -
<i>Coffea Arabica</i>	D ¹⁰⁵ VE ----- L ⁶⁰⁸ F ----- N ⁶²² L →3 aa← D ⁶²⁶ LC -
<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	D ¹⁰⁵ VE ----- L ⁵²⁸ F ----- S ⁶⁴² L →3 aa← D ⁶⁴⁶ LC -
<i>Zea mays</i>	D ¹⁰⁵ VE ----- L ⁵³¹ F ----- S ⁶⁴⁰ L →3 aa← D ⁶⁴³ LC -
<i>Oryza meyeriana</i>	D ¹⁰⁵ VE ----- L ³⁸⁹ F ----- S ⁴⁰³ L →3 aa← D ⁴⁰⁷ LC -
Nuclear-Encoded RNA Polymerases (NEPs) from Human & Animal Mitochondria[#]	
<i>Homo sapiens</i> (Human)	D ⁵⁴⁰ AE ----- M ⁸⁰¹ F ----- N ⁸¹⁵ L →3 aa← D ⁸¹⁹ VA -
<i>Pan troglodytes</i> (Chimpanzee)	D ⁵⁴⁰ AE ----- M ⁸⁰¹ F ----- N ⁸¹⁵ L →3 aa← D ⁸¹⁹ VA -
<i>Pongo abelii</i> (Orangutan)	D ⁵⁴⁰ TE ----- M ⁸⁰¹ F ----- N ⁸¹⁵ L →3 aa← D ⁸¹⁹ VA -
<i>Callithrix jacchus</i> (Monkey)	D ⁵³⁹ TE ----- M ⁸⁰⁰ F ----- N ⁸¹⁴ L →3 aa← D ⁸¹⁸ LA -
<i>Cavia porcellus</i> (Guinea pig)	D ⁵⁰⁷ TQ ----- M ⁷⁴⁷ F ----- N ⁷⁶¹ L →3 aa← D ⁷⁶⁵ LA -
<i>Mus musculus</i> (Mouse)	D ⁵¹² TQ ----- M ⁷⁷² F ----- N ⁷⁸⁶ L →3 aa← D ⁷⁹⁰ LA -
Mitochondrial DNA Polymerase γ from Human & Animals[#]	
<i>Homo sapiens</i> (Human)	D ¹⁹⁶ VE ----- F ²⁷⁴ R ----- Q ³⁹⁵ C →3 aa← D ³⁹⁹ VW -
<i>Pan troglodytes</i> (Chimpanzee)	D ¹⁹⁶ VE ----- F ²⁷² R ----- Q ³⁹³ C →3 aa← D ³⁹⁷ VW -
<i>Gorilla gorilla</i> (Gorilla)	D ¹⁹⁸ VE ----- F ²⁷⁴ R ----- Q ³⁹⁵ C →3 aa← D ³⁹⁹ VW -
<i>Mus musculus</i> (Mouse)	D ¹⁸¹ VE ----- F ²⁵⁷ R ----- Q ³⁷⁸ C →3 aa← D ³⁸² VW -
<i>Bos Taurus</i> (Bovine)	D ¹⁸² VE ----- F ²⁵⁸ R ----- Q ³⁷⁸ C →3 aa← D ³⁸² AW -
<i>Capra hircus</i> (Goat)	D ¹⁸² VE ----- F ²⁵⁸ R ----- Q ³⁷⁸ C →3 aa← D ³⁸² VW -
<i>Panthera leo</i> (Lion)	D ¹⁸⁶ VE ----- F ²⁶² R ----- Q ³⁸² C →3 aa← D ³⁸⁶ VW -
<i>Notechis scutatus</i> (Snake)	D ¹⁷⁷ VE ----- F ²⁷¹ R ----- Q ³⁷¹ C →3 aa← D ³⁷⁵ VQ -

Adapted from Palanivelu [58].

Sc, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*; *Hs*, *Homo sapiens*.

*The distance between the proton acceptor (H/Y) and the last D are highly conserved to 3 to 4 amino acids.

Active site amino acids confirmed by SDM analysis are highlighted in dark blue and by X-ray are highlighted in light blue.

Similar SDM-confirmed active site amino acids are found in *E. coli* DNA pol I

Table 3 Conserved catalytic core regions of various RNA and DNA polymerases

Polymerase type	Catalytic core
Viral T7 SSU RNA pol	- ⁶²⁰ WLA ^{Y⁸} GVT ^{R⁻⁴} SVT ^{K^{R1}} SVMTLA ^{Y⁸} GS-
Viral SP6 SSU RNA Pol	- ⁶¹² WDSI ^{I⁸} GIT ^{R⁻⁴} SLT ^{K^{K1}} PVMTLP ^{Y⁸} GS-
Mitochondrial RNA pol (<i>Sc</i>) (SSU)	- ¹⁰⁰⁹ TR ⁻⁴ KVV ^{K^{Q1}} TVMTNV ^{Y⁸} GV-
Mitochondrial RNA pol (<i>Hs</i>) (SSU)	- ⁹⁸⁶ TR ⁻⁴ KVV ^{K^{Q1}} TVMTVV ^{Y⁸} GV-
<i>E. coli</i> DNA pol I (SSU)	- ⁷⁵³ QR ⁻⁴ RSA ^{K³⁹} A ¹ INFLI ^{Y⁸} GM-
Chloroplast DNA pol IA (<i>ARATH</i>) (SSU)	- ⁸⁷³ ER ⁻⁴ RKAK ⁸⁷⁸ M ¹ LNFSIAY ⁸ GK-
Chloroplast DNA pol IB (<i>ARATH</i>) (SSU)	- ⁸⁵⁷ ER ⁻⁴ RKAK ⁸⁶² M ¹ LNFSIAY ⁸ GK-
Chloroplast RNA pol (NEP) (<i>ARATH</i>) (SSU)	- ⁷⁶⁴ DR ⁻⁴ KLV ^{K⁷⁹} Q ¹ TVMTSV ^{Y⁸} GV-
Mitochondrial RNA pol (NEP) (<i>ARATH</i>) (SSU)	- ⁷⁴⁷ DR ⁻⁴ KLV ^{K⁷³} Q ¹ TVMTSV ^{Y⁸} GV-
Mitochondrial RNA pol (NEP) (<i>Hs</i>) (SSU)*	- ⁹⁸⁶ TR ⁻⁴ KVV ^{K⁹⁹¹} Q ¹ TVMTVV ^{Y⁸} GV-
Mitochondrial DNA pol γ , POLG1 (<i>Hs</i>)*	- ⁹⁴² SR ⁻⁴ EHA ^{K⁹⁴⁷} I ¹ FNYGRIY ⁸ GA-

Adapted from Palanivelu [58]. *Present work.

Sc, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*; *ARATH*, *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Hs*, *Homo sapiens*;

The active site amino acids, highlighted in dark blue, are confirmed by SDM and other techniques.

4. Conclusion

Human mtDNA plays a crucial role in health and diseases [9, 59]. From the recent reports, it has become clear that mutations of *POLG1* are a major cause of many human diseases. For example, its damage is implicated in a larger number of human diseases, including neurodegenerative diseases (AD, HD, PD, ALS), cancer, diabetes, aging, etc. Many of the disease mutations are located in the DNA replicase (*POLG1*) gene. Therefore, the enzymes responsible for the mitochondrial DNA replication and transcription are analyzed for their polymerase and PR functions and their mutational consequences. The present study reveals that the mitochondrial DNA replicase, *POLG1*, shows a typical polymerase, DEDD(Y)-superfamily of PR exonuclease and (dRP)-lyase (BER) active site amino acids. Similarly, the mitochondrial RNA polymerase (NEP) also shows a typical polymerase, but DEDD(H)-superfamily of PR exonuclease active site amino acids. The polymerase and PR exonuclease active sites are in close agreement with the already reported RNA/DNA polymerases. The *POLG1* and its mtDNA replication repair pathways are limited and could not repair all types of mutations that occur in mtDNA. As the *POLG1* replicase possesses only the PR exonuclease and basic BER pathways, it is possible that the various lesions, adducts and double-stranded DNA breaks that occur on the mitochondrial genome are not repaired by these basic pathways, which could eventually lead to mtDNA damage/depletion, resulting in mitochondrial diseases. Two of the dominant mutations that cause heritable, autosomal mitochondrial diseases, viz. multi-systemic mitochondrial disease, Parkinsonism and PEO, are located within the *POLG1* catalytic core region. They are the nucleotide selection (R⁹⁴³) and template-binding (Y⁹⁵⁵) amino acids of the *POLG1* catalytic core.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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